
SOFC ZNE Home Final Report

Demonstration and Evaluation of a 1.5 kW Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) System for Mixed-Fuel Zero-Net-Energy (ZNE) Homes

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Executive Summary

In this addendum to our final report, the goal is to evaluate the potential role of solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC) for achieving zero net energy (ZNE) residential nanogrids in California by 2050. An optimal design and operation (dispatch) of an energy system including photovoltaic + SOFC + battery energy storage system (PV+SOFC+BESS) is achieved for a ZNE building in 2025, 2035, and 2045. For both the design and annual dispatch on an hourly basis, an optimization tool called DERopt is used for techno-economic analyses. The model selects the technologies that should be adopted, their size, and optimal operation to supply the annual building demand with the desired constraints (e.g., achieving zero net energy) at the lowest cost. For these analyses, three climate zones (CZ) of California were selected to represent diverse heating, cooling, and electric loads in the state, which CZ are also in SoCalGas service territory; CZ06 (LAX) for coastal areas, CZ15 (Brawley) for hot and dry areas with high cooling load, and CZ16 (Bishop) for colder areas with high heating loads.

The major findings of this final report addendum are as follows:

- Since SOFC can generate electricity continuously throughout the day, and since its waste heat can be used for domestic demands, it can play a role for decarbonizing the residential buildings, if there is a ZNE constraint.
- SOFC will only be optimally adopted if renewable gas can be delivered to residential buildings.
- Even though a renewable gas powered SOFC helps achieve a lower cost ZNE house in 2045, the building still needs to be first electrified with efficient heat pumps.
- Even though the utility cost of electricity is projected to increase in future, it is observed that the annual cost of energy to the homeowner goes down because of the reduction in PV and battery costs. Also, the battery operates on NEM 3.0 which adds to the value of having battery energy storage for its load shifting capabilities.

The optimization results clearly show that an SOFC-based ZNE solution is superior to solar PV and batteries alone. However, the results also clearly show that current ZNE solutions increase ratepayer cost of energy. Since cost efficiency is a key component of recommended and required Title 24 building energy efficiency standards, SOFC based systems are unlikely to be used widely unless both SOFC capital and renewable H₂ costs decrease significantly over the next 30 years.

Nomenclature

The nomenclature section summarizes general abbreviations, terms of art, and acronyms used throughout this report. This list does not include variables and parameters used in the optimization model. Model variable and parameter descriptions can be found in Section 4 Model Formulation.

ACC	Avoided Cost Calculator
BEopt	Building Energy Optimization Software
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
CEC	California Energy Commission
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CPUC	California Public Utilities Commission
CZ	Climate Zones
DC	Direct Current
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DERopt	Distributed Energy Resource Optimization Model
DG	Distributed Generation
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
EIA	Energy Information Administration
ESH	Electric Space Heater
ESS	Energy Storage System
EWH	Electric Water Heater
GSH	Gas Space Heater
GWH	Gas Water Heater
HP	Heat Pump
HR	Heat Recovery
HSPF	Heating and Seasonal Performance Factor
HW	Hot Water
ITC	Investment Tax Credit
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Electricity
LCOS	Levelized Cost of Storage
LHV	Lower Heating Value
LR	Learning Rate
MACRS	Modified Accelerated Cost Recovery System
MILP	Mixed Integer Linear Programming
NEM	Net Energy Metering
NG	Natural Gas

NREL	National Renewable Energy Laboratory
O&M	Operations and Maintenance
PV	Photovoltaic
SoC	State of Charge
R&D	Research and Development
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
REES	Renewable Electric Energy Storage
RPS	Renewable Portfolio Standard
SB	Senate Bill
SEER	Seasonal Energy Efficiency Ratio
SOFC	Solid Oxide Fuel Cell
SOFC mCHP	Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Micro Combined Heat and Power
TDV	Time Dependent Valuation
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
TOU	Time of Use
UCI	University of California, Irvine
UEF	Uniform Energy Factor
ZNE	Zero Net Energy

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

The goal of this report is to understand how solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) technology will fit into future residential buildings. Regulations established in 2008 mandated that all new single-family homes built in California achieve zero net energy (ZNE)¹, starting in 2020. This mandate is most commonly enforced through the California Energy Commission (CEC) Title 24 building energy efficiency standards [1], which mandates a series of energy efficiency and on-site renewable generation requirements for new construction and major retrofits. As of 2022, very few new buildings are truly ZNE due to cost effectiveness requirements: any new Title 24 standard must be cost effective to homeowners over 30 years.

Many clean energy technologies that support ZNE goals are currently not cost effective, leading to a recommendation for adoption, but not a requirement. These technologies include fuel cells, battery electric storage systems, and electrified or condensing gas space and water heating systems. However, clean energy technology and utility energy characteristics are steadily evolving, leading to the eventual shifting in technologies from being recommended to required. Achieving the goal of finding how SOFC technology will fit into future residential buildings necessitates finding the conditions under which SOFC systems achieve cost effectiveness while also supporting ZNE goals.

1.2 Literature Review

The process of selecting the lowest cost energy mix consists of technology adoption and operation, both of which must be considered simultaneously. This process is referred to as the techno-economic analysis and optimization of distributed energy resources (DER). Many studies have been conducted on techno-economic analysis and optimization of distributed energy resources (DER) for individual buildings and microgrids. There has been significant focus on cost-effectiveness and optimized operation of solar PV integrated with energy storage systems and grid (for the grid-tied microgrids) designed to achieve various goals. Multiple open-source tools are available for techno-economic analysis and optimization of hybrid energy systems.

The System Advisor Model (SAM) is developed by NREL and has been widely used by researchers for techno-economic studies and decision-making algorithms [2], [3]. A solar photovoltaic (PV) and electric battery was optimally sized in [4] by minimizing the loss of power supply probability (LPSP). An energy management method was proposed and tested through a hardware-in-loop assembly for experimental evaluation and the findings were validated by SAM. In another study, a solar PV/DC battery/local grid system was optimized by SAM for decarbonizing a university campus and maximizing the energy sharing in neighboring

¹ According to the California Department of General Services, a ZNE building is “An energy-efficient building where, on a source energy basis, the actual annual consumed energy is less than or equal to the on-site renewable generated energy.”: <https://www.cpuc.ca.gov/industries-and-topics/electrical-energy/demand-side-management/energy-efficiency/zero-net-energy>

communities [5]. Several case studies and techno-economic analyses and operation of PV/battery system using SAM are provided in the following references [6]–[9].

In some recent studies, cost minimization, optimal design and operation of PV/Battery systems are also subject to ZNE constraints. In [10], a linear program (LP) is developed that adapts to variable demand and solar PV generation in real-time to minimize the net grid usage by controlling the energy import, export and battery dispatch. The LP model is then integrated with SAM to consider non-linear storage and power conversion models. Integrated PV/Battery system for achieving ZNE residential buildings in four different climate zones in Arizona is studied in [11]. In this study, NREL's Building Energy Optimization software (BEopt) is used to model the building loads in each CZ and the data is used in SAM to determine the battery capacity for a maximum net present value (NPV).

Numerous techno-economic design and dispatch optimization of integrated PV/Battery for buildings has been studied with other building energy tools such as TRNSYS , JEPlus, and HOMER [12]. Building energy models from TRNSYS are usually integrated with multi-objective optimization tools [13]. An extensive technical optimization is conducted on a high-rise residential building in Hong Kong through coupled modelling and optimizations with TRNSYS and JEPlus + EA [14], [15]. Different scenarios of an off-grid resort equipped with PV, battery, and thermal energy storage are simulated in TRNSYS and are optimized for minimum life cycle cost using the GenOpt optimization tool [16]. GenOpt uses a particle swarm algorithm to support multi-parameter optimizations, and can be coupled with external simulation program (e.g., EnergyPlus, TRNSYS, and Dymola [17]). HOMER Grid is used for techno-economic analysis and optimization of grid-tied PV, wind turbine, and battery for a university campus in a tsunami-affected region in Indonesia [18].

A mixed integer linear program (MILP) optimization is proposed in [19] to allocate and dispatch solar PV and battery systems across an Advanced Energy Communities (AEC) such that net electrical imports are fully balanced by export. The model is developed in an open-source tool called Distributed Energy Resource Optimization (DERopt) that is described in [20]. DERopt finds the optimal design and operation of different distributed generation (DG) such as gas turbine CHPs, PV, electrical and thermal energy storage systems. Studies that used DERopt for optimal sizing and dispatch of DG in microgrids for different applications could be found in [20]–[23].

Despite highly available research in the field of techno-economic analysis PV/Battery systems and optimized dispatch of batteries for electrified buildings, the cost-effectiveness of considering renewable gas in building energy mix is not thoroughly studied. A few papers have been published that focus on optimization of fuel cell based microgrids and techno-economic analysis of renewable gas consumption for residential buildings. In [24], a reversible solid oxide cell (rSOC) based microgrid is optimally designed to meet the electrical and thermal demand of a residential complex (20-unit) in Italy together with the electricity and fuel demand for residents' electric and H₂ fuel cell vehicles. The microgrid is grid tied and the rSOC is coupled with PV and wind as renewable sources.

A recent review article provides a literature survey of techno-economic analysis and optimization of hybrid renewable energy system including PV, battery, wind turbines integrated with hydrogen technologies, electrolyzers, and fuel cells [25], [26]. It categorizes the available papers based on

the optimization tools (HOMER, TRNSYS, ...), methods (MILP, mixed integer non-linear program (MINLP), bi-level mixed-integer (BLMI), iterative method, ...), and provides limitation and advantages of different algorithms (genetic, mine blast, whale, bee-inspired, harmony search, particle swarm, ...). The objective of most of these almost 200 papers were minimization of cost of energy, net present value (NPV), LPSP, and CO₂ emissions, not ZNE operation.

With increasing focus on ZNE buildings, more research is needed on ZNE constraint to the optimization of DER systems integrated with hydrogen technologies. The economic feasibility of renewable energy systems integrated with hydrogen technologies to achieve ZNE large-scale buildings are available in a few papers; In [27], a pumped hydro storage and PEM fuel cell taxis were optimally sized and integrated into renewable energy sources to achieve a ZNE commercial building in China. A grid-tied integrated system of SOFC, PV, and battery is proposed in [28] to evaluate the effect of a natural gas fed SOFC in achieving ZNE residential building in California. This research focuses on the California Title 24 building energy code, which uses a time resolve source energy metric, or the Time Dependent Valuation (TDV) or energy, to define ZNE. Required PV capacity to satisfy the TDV based ZNE constraint is assessed in 16 climate zones of California. Though it gives an insight about having an SOFC and mixed-fuel (gas/electric) appliance versus all-electric buildings, the study does not provide economic feasibility of such a system. The proposed dispatch algorithms only maximize the building self-consumption and minimize the grid reliance without considering revenue making or cost minimization.

The cost-effectiveness of all-electric vs. mixed-fuel (gas/electric) residential buildings in California is studied at Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory [29]. The study provides a techno-economic analysis for ZNE homes in 16 California climate zones using 2022 Title 24 TDV factor; It concludes that in most areas, the life-cycle cost of all-electric and mixed-fuel are comparable due to the savings from avoided natural gas infrastructure. The grid-tied building is equipped with PV/battery system and the exported electricity is assumed to be offset under the future net energy metering (NEM 3.0) rates in California; NEM 3.0 has less compensation rates for avoided costs by PV export compared to NEM 2.0 which is more favorable for solar export. The Building Energy Optimization Tool (BEopt) is used to simulate the building loads with gas and electric heating appliances to compare the mixed-fuel vs. all-electric ZNE homes. The impact of having an SOFC mCHP and thermal energy storage system in realization of California's ZNE goals and economic feasibility is yet to be investigated.

Deployment of CHP units in houses has been proved to be an impactful energy efficient measure. The role of installing CHP units in residential buildings in carbon emission, primary energy consumption for the heat and electricity demands is presented in [30]. In a European-wide demonstration project, 1046 units of residential fuel cell mCHPs were deployed within 5 years in 10 EU member states [31]. Out of all mCHP units, 603 were SOFC and 443 were PEM. The analyses proved that compared to no mCHP, installing 1 kW of mCHP decreased €6,000 of infrastructure and operating costs as well as 370 – 1,100 kg CO₂ emission per year.

1.3 Current Work and Contributions

The goal of the current work is to understand how SOFC technology will fit into future residential buildings. A generalized schematic of the problem is shown in Figure 1. This figure shows a house receiving both electrical and natural gas utility service. The property owner has the option of adopting, solar PV, and electric battery, and a SOFC. All DER assets work together with electric utility service to meet home electric demand. In addition to electricity, waste heat from the SOFC can be used to produce domestic hot water². Waste heat recovery is managed in conjunction with typical hot water systems to meet building domestic hot water (DHW) demand. Finally, space heating systems are operated to meet building thermal demand. This techno-economic problem is considered “solved” once lowest cost has been achieved and all ZNE, technical, and economic constraints have been satisfied.

Figure 1: Schematic of the general DER design and operation problem considered in this work

An optimal configuration of a nanogrid system including PV, battery, SOFC mCHP, and thermal energy storage is proposed to achieve TDV based ZNE (TDV-ZNE) in California. The residential building is tied to both gas and electric grid to evaluate different building heating scenarios (electrified and gas heating appliances). The objective function is defined in DERopt [20] to find the optimized dispatch profile of each energy technology to achieve minimum life cycle cost using MILP. The building loads in each scenario is obtained from *Building* Energy Optimization Tool (BEopt) for a prototype single-family housing. Three climate zones of SoCalGas with extremely different heating and cooling demand are selected for the research: CZ06 (along the ocean with

² SOFC heat recovery can also be used to help meet space heating loads. This type of combined heat and power, however is not considered in the current work since conventional SOFC heat recovery systems involve exhaust gas – water heat exchanger. The hot water produced through this heat recovery process is immediately useful for domestic hot water systems and radiant space heating systems, but would require additional engineering for integration with a central furnace system. Since most homes in California use either central or wall mounted furnaces, waste heat recovery for space heating is not considered in this work.

mild heating and cooling load), CZ15(hot summers with high cooling load), and CZ16 (cold winter with high heating load). These three climate zones were used in place of all 16 climate zones due to being found as representative of all climate zones. Designs for each building model are developed for three subsequent decades from 2020 through 2050, using 2025, 2035, and 2045 as reference years.

2 Building Energy Load Development

The current work relies on existing building energy model (BEM) prototypes. These prototype models are designed to capture energy use in a typical building. Prototype development has historically focused on commercial buildings [32], [33], but more recent efforts have produced residential prototype BEMs [34], [35]. When using a prototype model, a major consideration is the climate zone (CZ). Title 24 codes are designed to require efficiency measures specific to each CZ since weather has an obvious effect on building energy use, and since Title 24 requirements are tailored to each CZ. This section first describes the process used for selecting California CZs for detailed analysis. After CZ selection, the subsequent section describes the development of BEM based on a prototype single-family detached home tailored to each specific climate zone.

2.1 Climate Zone Selection

The California Energy Commission (CEC) established 16 climate zones (CZ) [36] for use in the development of State initiatives, regulations, and standards, such as the California Title 24 building energy efficiency code [1]. A reference city, heating degree days (HDD), and cooling degree days (CDD) for the 16 climate zones are shown in Table 1 [37].

Table 1: Reference city, heating degree days, and cooling degree days for the 16 CEC climate zones. Values are taken from [37].

Climate Zone	Reference City	Heating Degree Day (Base 65°F)	Cooling Degree Day (Base 80°F)
1	Eureka	4496	0
2	Napa	2844	456
3	Oakland	2909	128
4	San Jose	2335	574
5	Santa Maria	2844	456
6	Los Angeles (LAX)	1458	727
7	San Diego	1256	984
8	Long Beach	1430	1201
9	Los Angeles (Civic Center)	1154	1537
10	Riverside	1678	1456
11	Red Bluff	2688	1904
12	Stockton	2702	1470
13	Fresno	2702	1470
14	Barstow	2581	4239
15	Brawley	1106	6565
16	Bishop	4313	1037

Instead of analyzing all 16 climate zones, a reduced set was selected for analysis. Figure 1 shows CDD and HDD for all climate zones. Since this work is primarily focused on Southern California, Northern California CZs were excluded (shown in Figure 1 with green circles). Among the 11 remaining CZs (shown as blue diamonds), CZ15 Brawley and CZ16 Bishop were selected due to having the highest CDD or HDD, respectively. CZ06 Los Angeles (LAX) was selected as the third CZ. In total, the other 13 CZs are similar to or fall between the three selected CZs. Prior work has shown that residential energy use across all 16 climate zones is similar to or bounded by these three CZs [29]. Additionally, this work showed that energy use in CZ1, or the coldest climate zone based on cited data [37] is similar to CZ16 Hourly weather data for 2020 for the three selected CZs was collected from the National Solar Radiation Data Base [38].

Figure 2: Cooling and heating degree days for the 16 climate zones. Green dots and blue diamonds show all CA climate zones. However, for selection, only Southern California climate zones were considered. Climate zones selected for analysis are indicated with orange circles.

Climate zone selection is based solely on heating and cooling degree days and does not consider population density in each zone.. Most California residents live in climate zones that are similar to CZ06 (Los Angeles Airport). In general, results from this climate zone are most illustrative of the optimal DER system in other climate zones. CZ15 and CZ16 are provided to capture the entire residential building design space, but should not necessarily be taken as leading indicators of optimal DER design in all other climate zones.

2.2 Building Energy Modeling

The building energy model (BEM) was based on the work originally presented in [29]. The Building Energy Optimization Tool (BEopt) tool [39] was used to recreate the CEC prototype single-family detached one-story building described in [40] and [41]. The prototype envelope and floor area end use are shown in Figure 2 along with the BEopt BEM geometry and layout. This

figure also provides climate specific BEM settings that are outlined in Title 24 Alternative Calculation Method Reference Manual [40]. Appliance, plug loads, and internal gains are based on the ANSI/RESNET/ICC 301-2014 Standard.

Figure 3: One-story single family detached prototype BEM specification and model overview. Subfigures show (a) building exterior [41] and (c) floor plan [41], and the corresponding BEM (b and d).

Six appliance and building energy system configurations are considered in this work:

1. **Baseline:** The baseline scenario assumes standard natural gas appliances and heating systems, including a 78% natural gas central furnace, 13 seasonal energy efficiency ratio (SEER) central air conditioning system, and a 0.6 uniform energy factor (UEF) 50-gallon tank domestic hot water (DHW) heater.
2. **Premium gas:** The premium gas scenario is the same as the Baseline except that the space heater has been replaced with a 98% efficient condensing gas space heater and a 0.96 UEF on-demand, condensing DHW heater.
3. **Electric Resistive:** This scenario assumes that all appliances have been electrified. The central gas furnace has been replaced with a 100% efficiency central electric resistive furnace. The gas water heater has been replaced with a 0.9 UEF 50 gallon tank DHW heater.
4. **Premium Electric Resistive:** This scenario is the same as the “Electric Resistive” scenario except that the DHW heater is replaced with a 0.99 UEF on-demand electric resistive DHW heater.
5. **Heat Pump:** This scenario assumes that all appliances have been electrified. The central furnace and AC system have been replaced with a reversible operating at 14 SEER cooling and 8.2 heating and seasonal performance factor (HSPF). These values

are based on minimum 2019 Title 24 air-source reversible heat pump performance standards [1]. This scenario also assumes that a 3.0 UEF 50-gallon tank hot water heat pump (HWHP) has replaced the gas tank system.

6. **Premium Heat Pump:** This scenario is the same as the “Heat Pump” scenario except that the reversible heat pump has been replaced with an air-sourced, mini-split heat pump system operating at 29.3 SEER and 14 HSPF [42]–[44]. This is the only scenario that includes a higher efficiency central AC system.

3 Energy Cost Components

DERopt optimization performance depends directly on the quality of techno-economic inputs used to predict the cost and value of different actions. This section describes the data sources and projection methods used to estimate how these different inputs will evolve over the next 30 years.

3.1 Time Dependent Value of Energy

The time dependent value of energy consists of two metrics which are used to estimate the cost of and fossil energy used in the delivery of utility electricity and natural gas. These metrics were created in support of the Title 24 California energy efficiency building code. By law, any measure that is mandated under Title 24 must be shown to reduce cost for ratepayers while also reducing fossil energy use. Both the cost and energy TDV metrics recognize that utility electricity and natural gas supply changes throughout the day, between seasons, and across years. These metrics estimate the hourly cost and fossil intensity for delivering energy to ratepayers from 2022 through 2052. Both metrics were developed using utility energy procurement models that assume 1) California utilities will be able to procure sufficient renewable resources to meet State carbon emission goals, and 2) that these resources will be selected to minimize total cost [45]. The output of these models are a set of cost and energy metrics that share common units, allowing for comparison of different building code requirements regardless of energy/fuel source.

The 2019 TDV energy metric is used in this work, but not the TDV cost metric. The TDV cost metric is designed to be utility and rate independent, allowing for analysis across different utility service territories. Since this work is exclusively focused on the SoCalGas and SCE territory, applicable rate tariffs are used in-place of the TDV cost. The utility cost models used in this work are described in Sections 3.2 and 3.3.

The daily average TDV energy intensity of electricity for three years spanning from 2025 through 2045 is shown in Figure 3. These values account for generation, transmission, and distribution of electricity. This figure also shows the average TDV electricity energy intensity between 2020 and 2050. All curves show differences between solar and non-solar hours along with a steady decline in TDV energy over time. This decline is driven by an increasing quantity of renewable energy resources installed across the State paired with storage resources used to shift renewable production to meet demand that would have been otherwise met using fossil resources.

Figure 4: Average TDV energy intensity for utility electricity in 2025, 2035, 2045, and the average from 2020 through 2050.

The TDV energy intensity of natural gas accounts for gas transmission, distribution, and end use. According to the current “policy compliant” TDV values, the nonrenewable energy intensity of natural gas will linearly decline from 0.97 kBtu primary energy per kBtu of delivered gas in 2023, to 0.755 kBtu primary energy per kBtu delivered gas in 2050. Notably, the TDV energy content of natural gas does not decline to zero by 2050, likely due to limited renewable fuel sources. This is accounted for within the TDV energy model through carbon cap and trade offsets that increase the cost of natural gas over time. This component is considered when developing future gas cost projections.

3.2 Utility Electricity Rates

This work uses current retail residential utility time-of-use rates [46] augmented using cost projections based on initial projections associated with reaching California environmental goals [47]. Current retail time of use rates track the general 2025 TDV electricity energy profile shown in Figure 4. Electricity costs are highest in the early evening, lowest in the middle of the day, and at an intermediate point at all other hours. These rates effectively follow the “duck-curve” created with large quantities of utility solar coming offline in the early evening [48].

These retail rate were projected into the future based on initial analysis on meeting California Senate Bill 100 (SB100) renewable electricity goals [49]. According to this analysis, the cost of energy will increase to \$0.148 per kWh at 60% renewable electricity supply in 2035, up to \$0.171 per kWh at 100% renewable electricity supply in 2045. This was captured in our work by increasing utility energy charges until the average charge matched these SB100 projections. The SB100 analysis did not predict changes in transmission and distribution charges, nor did it examine expansions to the electric transmission and distribution system. As a result, these retail cost components were held constant into the future.

In addition to addressing the cost of importing electricity, utility rates also govern the value of exported electricity. Current export rates across California are governed under “Net Energy Metering 2.0”, or NEM 2.0. Under this structure, exported electricity produces a credit equal to the time of use electricity rate minus a non-bypassable charge between \$0.01 and \$0.02 per exported kWh. NEM 2.0 rates apply as long as the sum of credits generated from export are less

than the value of imported electricity.

The California Public Utilities Commission has proposed the replacement of NEM 2.0 with NEM 3.0 [50]. Under NEM 3.0, export rates would be based on an “avoided cost” that is, in part, based on wholesale electricity rates. NEM 3.0 rates are projected through 2050 using the “Avoided Cost Calculator” [51]. Timing of NEM 3.0 implementation is unknown, so the current work assumes that this rate structure will not be implemented until late 2020s.

Both NEM 2.0 and 3.0 are primarily targeted at ratepayers with behind the meter solar and batteries paired with renewable resources. Batteries that are charged using any nonrenewable resources are ineligible for export under NEM rates. Fuel cell, however, systems are eligible for export under NEM rates if the carbon intensity of exported electricity falls below targets set by the California Air Resources Board [52]. The method for calculating the carbon intensity limit is defined under California Code of Regulations Title 17 Section 95412. For reference, the 2025 limit is 312 kg CO_{2e}per MWh. This limit will linearly decline by 13.4 kg CO_{2e}per MWh per year.

3.3 Utility Gas Rates

Utility gas rates are based on residential natural gas rates through Southern California Gas company. Natural gas rates consist of transmission and distribution, and procurement costs. While transmission and distribution costs have remained stable over the past decade, procurement costs can vary widely month to month. Instead of developing a projection of gas prices, procurement cost assumed to be the average price of procurement between 2010 and 2020, or approximately \$0.40 per therm [53]. Note that the U.S. Energy Information Administration projects the cost in 2021 dollars of bulk natural gas to decrease slightly from now to 2050 [54].

Under a 100% conventional natural gas scenario and the gas mixture used for calculating the TDV energy content of natural gas, a stationary fuel cell operating using retail natural gas is ineligible for the export under any NEM tariff. For example, fuel cell carbon intensity must be at or below 178 kg CO_{2e}per MWh in 2035, and at or below 44 kg CO_{2e}per MWh in 2045. Assuming a 60% LHV efficient fuel cell, pipeline natural gas renewable content must reach 46% and 86% respectively in order to satisfy these emission requirements. However, TDV energy calculations predict a renewable fraction of 26% in 2050. As a result, additional renewable fuel must be added to the retail natural gas mix. This work assumes that this additional natural gas is supplied through expanded renewable hydrogen (H₂) production. Sufficient H₂ is added such that the carbon intensity requirement is satisfied for a 60% efficient generator. Cost of hydrogen is taken from the [55], or \$6 per kg in 2025, \$4.5 per kg in 2035, and \$4 per kg in 2045.

Finally, a cost adder associated with carbon emission abatement is included. Cost of carbon is taken from the TDV value calculations for natural gas. This cost is added to the price of utility gas based on the non-renewable carbon content portion of utility gas.

3.4 Equipment Costs

Equipment costs captured in this work include solar PV, electric batteries, SOFC and heat recovery systems, space heating equipment, and DHW equipment. Although the optimization model does not actively select between different space and water heating equipment, these costs are included

in post-optimization analysis to understand differences in total investment and energy costs associated with any specific scenario.

Solar PV and battery energy storage costs are based on the “residential – conservative” scenarios defined in the 2022 Annual Technology Baseline provided by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory [56]. Solar PV and battery energy storage systems charged using renewable electricity are assumed to receive a tax credit of 25%. Batteries that can be charged from the electric grid receive no tax credit. Capital cost and performance parameters of a 5 kW fuel cell (without specifying the type) are provided in U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA) database [57].

Space and water heating cost projections are generated based on a combination of building cost estimation tools and projections. First, HWHP and ducted space heating heat pump equipment costs for all years are estimated using the cost projections presented in [58]. Cost estimates for high performance ductless space heating heat pumps are not widely available, so this cost was assumed to be 50% higher than the ducted heat pump cost projection provided in [58]. 20205 costs for all other equipment types were estimated using the RS Means green building cost estimation software [59]. We assumed that all equipment costs aside from condensing gas systems would remain constant through time due to technology maturity and ubiquity. We assumed that condensing natural gas space and water heater system cost would decline over time. Cost projections were not readily available, so we assumed that condensing gas equipment costs would decline at similar rates as heat pump systems.

4 DERopt Model

The DERopt techno-economic optimization model is formulated as a mixed integer linear program. This type of problem includes a combination of integer, binary, and continuous decisions. In general, integer decisions are associated with the adoption of discrete energy systems (i.e., a fuel cell), binary decisions are associated with achieving equipment operational state and/or specific operational requirements (i.e., achieving a sufficiently low fuel cell electricity carbon intensity to enable export), and continuous decisions are associated with energy flows. The general form of optimization problem is in the following form[60]:

$$(1) \text{ minimize } f(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{e})$$

$f(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{e})$: objective function

Subject to:

$$\mathbf{S}^{min} \leq \mathbf{S} < \mathbf{S}^{max} \quad \mathbf{S}: \text{ set of design variables (type/size of each component)}$$

$$\mathbf{e}^{min} \leq \mathbf{e} < \mathbf{e}^{max} \quad \mathbf{e}: \text{ set of control variables (dispatch variables of each component)}$$

$$\mathbf{g}_i(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{e}) \leq \mathbf{0} \quad : \text{ inequality constraints}$$

$$\mathbf{h}_i(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{e}) = \mathbf{0} \quad : \text{ equality constraints}$$

In the current work, the objective function, $f(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{e})$, is a cost function that minimizes the total annual cost of energy. DER technologies includes solar PV, SOFC, and battery systems. The model also includes utility gas and electricity connections. The model also allows from the building back to the grid to increase savings and/or achieve ZNE. This section described the DERopt model in detail.

4.1 Introduction of sets, decision variables, and parameters used in DERopt

The following set is used in the cost function model:

- $t \in T$: Set of all hourly increments in a year

Table 2. List of parameters used in DERopt model

Building	Description	Unit
$d_{el-bldg,t}$	Building electric energy demand during time t	kWh
$d_{th-bldg,t}$	Building thermal energy demand during time t	kWh
$d_{hw-bldg,t}$	Building hot water energy demand during time t	kWh
Utility Cost Parameters		
$C_{el-imp,t}$	Cost of utility electricity imported at time t	\$/kWh
$C_{el-exp,t}$	Cost of electricity exported to the grid at time t	\$/kWh
$C_{g-imp,t}$	Cost of utility gas imported at time t	\$/kWh

$C_{CO_2,t}$	Carbon emission cost of utility electricity at time t	\$/therm
DER	Description	Unit
Solar Photovoltaic (PV)		
C_{PV}^{cap}	Capital cost of solar PV system	\$/kW
$C_{PV}^{O\&M}$	O&M cost of solar PV system (0.001)	\$/kWh
η_{PV}	Conversion efficiency of each kW/m ² of solar radiation to electricity under the standard test conditions (20)	% of kW/m ²
$e_{insol,t}$	Solar insolation during t	kWh/m ²
A_{max-PV}	Max area available for PV installation (200)	m ²
Electric Energy Storage (EES) and Renewable EES (REES)		
$C_{EES}^{cap}, C_{REES}^{cap}$	Capital cost of EES, REES	\$/kWh
$C_{EES,ch}^{O\&M}, C_{REES,ch}^{O\&M}$	O&M cost to charge EES, REES (0.001)	\$/kWh
$C_{EES,dch}^{O\&M}, C_{REES,dch}^{O\&M}$	O&M cost to discharge EES, REES (0.001)	\$/kWh
$\bar{\delta}_{EES}, \bar{\delta}_{REES}$	Maximum EES/REES state of charge (95)	% Capacity
$\underline{\delta}_{EES}, \underline{\delta}_{REES}$	Minimum EES/ REES state of charge (10)	% Capacity
$\bar{\mu}_{EES}, \bar{\mu}_{REES}$	Maximum EES/ REES charging rate (50)	% Capacity
$\underline{\mu}_{EES}, \underline{\mu}_{REES}$	Maximum EES/ REES discharging rate (50)	% Capacity
$\eta_{EES,ch}, \eta_{REES,ch}$	EES/REES charging efficiency (90)	%
$\eta_{EES,dch}, \eta_{REES,dch}$	EES/REES discharging efficiency (90)	%
$\alpha_{EES}, \alpha_{REES}$	Self-discharge rate of EES/REES (99.99)	%
Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC)		
C_{SOFC}^{cap}	Capital cost of SOFC system	\$/kW _e
$C_{SOFC}^{O\&M}$	O&M cost of SOFC system (6 % of C_{SOFC}^{cap})	\$/kW _e
η_{e-SOFC}	SOFC electric efficiency (60)	%
$\eta_{hw-SOFC}$	SOFC heat/hot water generation efficiency (30)	%
S_{SOFC}	Size of a unit SOFC system (0.5)	kW
P_{SOFC}^{min}	SOFC minimum load setting (50% of rated power)	kW
$R_{rmp-SOFC}$	SOFC ramping up /down rate (6)	%
Thermal Energy Storage (TES)		
$\bar{\delta}_{TES}$	Maximum TES tank state of charge (80 gallon / 20 kWh)	20 kWh
$\eta_{TES,ch}$	TES charging efficiency (95)	%
$\eta_{TES,dch}$	TES discharging efficiency (95)	%
α_{TES}	Self-discharge rate of TES (99.99)	%
Building space heating and hot water equipment		
η_{GSH}	Gas space heater efficiency	%
η_{GWH}	Gas water heater efficiency	%
η_{ESH}	Electric space heater efficiency	%
η_{EWH}	Electric water heater efficiency	%
Conversion factor (power to energy)		
Δt	Hourly time step (1)	hour

Variable	Description	Type & Number
Electricity and Gas Utility Variables		
$e_{gr-imp,t}$	Electricity imported from the grid at time t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$e_{gr-exp,t}$	Electricity exported to the grid at time t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$g_{gr-imp,t}$	Gas imported from the grid at time t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
Solar Photovoltaic (PV)		
S_{PV}	PV system size purchased (kW)	Continuous 1
$e_{el-PV,t}$	PV electricity directly used for building during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$e_{st-PV,t}$	PV electricity stored in the battery during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$e_{exp-PV,t}$	PV electricity exported to the grid during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
Battery (EES)		
S_{EES}	EES capacity adopted (kWh)	Continuous 1
$e_{ch-EES,t}$	Electricity charged by EES during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$e_{dch-EES,t}$	EES electricity discharged to building during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$e_{EES,t}$	EES state of charge during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
Battery (REES)		
S_{REES}	REES capacity adopted (kWh)	Continuous 1
$e_{ch-REES,t}$	Electricity charged by REES during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$e_{dch-REES,t}$	REES electricity discharged to building during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$e_{exp-REES,t}$	REES electricity exported to the grid during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$e_{REES,t}$	REES state of charge during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC)		
N_{SOFC}	Number of installed SOFC systems with 0.5 kW capacity	Integer 1
$e_{SOFC,t}$	SOFC electricity output during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$hw_{SOFC,t}$	Hot water directly used for building during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
Thermal Energy Storage (TES)		
$hw_{dch-TES,t}$	Hot water discharged from TES tank during t	Continuous 8760
$hw_{ch-TES,t}$	SOFC cogenerated hot water stored in TES during t	Continuous

		8760
$hw_{TES,t}$	TES state of charge during t	Continuous 8760
Building space heating and hot water heater equipment		
S_{GSH}	Gas space heater (GSH) capacity (kW)	Continuous 1
$g_{GSH,t}$	Gas consumption by GSH during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
S_{GWH}	Gas water heater (GWH) capacity (kW)	Continuous 1
$g_{GWH,t}$	Gas consumption by GWH during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
S_{ESH}	Electric space heater (ESH) capacity (kW)	Continuous 1
$e_{ESH,t}$	Electricity consumption by ESH during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
S_{EWH}	Electric water heater (EWH) capacity (kW)	Continuous 1
$e_{EWH,t}$	Electricity consumption by EWH during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760

For electric space and water heaters, different technologies are considered: electric resistive heaters with efficiencies equal or less than 100%; and heat pumps with coefficient of performance greater than 1. In this work, we show both types of electric heaters versus gas heaters, while the efficiency values vary depending on the technology type. Details of these heating technologies are provided in Section 2.2.

4.2 Cost Function

The objective function (shown in Equation (1)) is the total annualized cost of building energy. This includes utility bills, equipment capital, and equipment O&M. Fixed costs depend on the capacity of different energy supply and storage units that are purchased for the building. The size of each component (SOFC, PV, EES, and REES - shown as S_i) and the output energy from each component or utility source at each time step (shown as e_i) is a decision variable of the problem.

$$\begin{aligned}
f(S, e) = & \left(S_{PV} C_{PV}^{cap} + \sum_1^{8760} (e_{el-PV,t} + e_{st-PV,t} + e_{exp-PV,t}) C_{PV}^{O\&M} \right) \\
& + \left(S_{EES} C_{EES}^{cap} + \sum_1^{8760} (e_{dch-EES,t} + e_{ch-EES,t}) C_{EES}^{O\&M} \right) \\
& + \left(S_{REES} C_{REES}^{cap} + \sum_1^{8760} (e_{dch-REES,t} + e_{exp-REES,t} + e_{ch-REES,t}) C_{REES}^{O\&M} \right) \\
& + \left(S_{SOFC} C_{SOFC}^{cap} + \sum_1^{8760} e_{SOFC,t} C_{SOFC}^{O\&M} + \sum_1^{8760} \frac{e_{SOFC,t}}{\eta_{el-SOFC}} C_{g-imp,t} \right) \\
& + \left(\sum_1^{8760} g_{gr-imp,t} C_{g-imp,t} \right) + \left(\sum_1^{8760} e_{gr-imp,t} C_{el-imp,t} \right) \\
& - \left(\sum_1^{8760} e_{gr-exp,t} C_{el-exp,t} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

The total gas imported from the grid during time step t is shown in (2).

$$g_{gr-imp,t} = \frac{e_{SOFC,t}}{\eta_{el-SOFC}} C_{g-imp,t} + g_{GWH,t} + g_{GSH,t} \tag{3}$$

All decision variables must be equal to or greater than zero (lower bound). Equality and inequality constraints are set to ensure the following:

- All building energy demands (electricity, heating, and hot water) are met at any given time
- At the end of the year, the total time dependent value of imported energy is less than or equal to the total time dependent value of exported energy
- The energy output from each DER equipment is limited by its installed capacity
- Since battery is allowed to only export renewable electricity to the grid, REES is constrained to be charged only by PV; also, it is the only battery that discharges electricity to the grid and building. EES electricity is only discharged to the building.
- The charging/discharging energy of all batteries are limited to their capacities and the maximum charge/discharge rates; also, their state of charges is limited to the allowable

minimum and maximum levels

- Ramp up and ramp down rate of SOFC are limited to reduce the wear and tear from thermal cycle and mechanical stress. In this the ramping rate is limited to 0.5 W/s (1.8 kW/h) to avoid rapid SOFC dynamics [61].

The minimum partial load of SOFC is assumed to be 50% of its maximum capacity to avoid its complete cool down and start-up costs. The complete list of constraints is provided in Table 3.

Table 3. Equality and inequality constraints to be satisfied by the optimal solution from DERopt

General constraints (equalities)	
Description	Formula
Electricity demand	$d_{el-bldg,t} + e_{ch-EES,t} + e_{EWH,t} + e_{ESH,t}$ $= e_{el-PV,t} + e_{el-SOFC,t} + e_{dch-EES,t} + e_{dch-REES,t}$ $+ e_{gr-imp,t}$
Space heating demand	$d_{th-bldg,t} = g_{GSH,t} \eta_{GSH} + e_{ESH,t} \eta_{ESH}$
Domestic hot water demand	$d_{hw-bldg,t} = g_{GWH,t} \eta_{GWH} + e_{ERH,t} \eta_{ERH} + hw_{SOFC,t} + hw_{dch-RES,t}$
Grid and utility interactions constraints (inequalities)	
Electricity export income does not exceed the electricity import cost	$(e_{exp-PV,t} + e_{exp-REES,t}) C_{el-exp,t} \leq e_{gr-imp,t} C_{el-imp,t}$
Total electricity export does not exceed the electricity import	$\sum_1^{8760} (e_{exp-PV,t} + e_{exp-REES,t}) \leq \sum_1^{8760} e_{gr-imp,t}$
Zero net energy (ZNE) constraint based on time dependent value (TDV) of primary energy	$\sum_1^{8760} e_{gr-imp,t} TDV_{el,imp,t} + \sum_1^{8760} g_{gr-imp,t} TDV_{g,imp,t} \leq$ $\sum_1^{8760} e_{exp-PV,t} TDV_{el,exp,t} + \sum_1^{8760} e_{exp-REES,t} TDV_{el,exp,t}$
PV constraints (inequalities)	
Installed PV capacity is limited by maximum area	$S_{PV} \leq \eta_{PV} A_{max-PV}$
PV output is limited by the installed capacity (t = 1 hr)	$e_{el-PV,t} + e_{st-PV,t} + e_{exp-PV,t} \leq S_{PV} t$
PV production is limited by the available solar insolation at a given time	$e_{el-PV,t} + e_{st-PV,t} + e_{exp-PV,t} \leq e_{insol,t} \frac{S_{PV}}{\eta_{PV}}$
Battery (EES) constraints	
Same initial & final SOC	$e_{EES,0} \leq e_{EES,8760}$
EES energy balance	$e_{EES,t} = e_{EES,(t-1)} \alpha_{EES} + \eta_{EES, ch} e_{ch-EES,t} - \frac{e_{dch-EES,t}}{\eta_{EES, dch}}$
Limit EES state of charge to its installed capacity	$\underline{\delta}_{EES} S_{EES} \leq e_{EES,t} \leq \bar{\delta}_{EES} S_{EES}$
Limit EES charging rate	$0 \leq e_{ch-EES,t} \leq \bar{\mu}_{EES} S_{EES}$
Limit EES discharging rate	$0 \leq e_{dch-EES,t} \leq \underline{\mu}_{EES} S_{EES}$
Battery (REES) constraints	
Initial REES electricity exported to the grid	$e_{exp-REES,0} = 0$

REES energy balance	$e_{REES,t} = e_{REES,(t-1)} \alpha_{REES} + \eta_{REES_{ch}} e_{ch-REES,t} - \frac{(e_{dch-REES,t} + e_{exp-REES,t})}{\eta_{REES_{dch}}}$
Limit REES state of charge to its installed capacity	$\underline{\delta}_{REES} S_{REES} \leq e_{REES,t} \leq \bar{\delta}_{REES} S_{REES}$
Limit REES charging rate	$0 \leq e_{ch-REES,t} \leq \bar{\mu}_{REES} S_{REES}$
Limit REES discharging rate	$0 \leq (e_{dch-REES,t} + e_{exp-REES,t}) \leq \underline{\mu}_{REES} S_{REES}$
SOFC constraints	
Electricity generated by SOFC is limited by the number and size of SOFCs and their minimum load	$N_{SOFC} S_{SOFC} P_{SOFC}^{min} \leq e_{SOFC,t} \leq N_{SOFC} S_{SOFC}$
Hot water recovery from SOFC is limited to electricity output and efficiency	$hw_{SOFC,t} + hw_{ch-RES,t} \leq \frac{e_{SOFC,t}}{\eta_{e-SOFC}} \eta_{hw-SOFC}$
Limit SOFC ramp-up rate	$e_{SOFC,t} - e_{SOFC,(t-1)} \leq R_{rmp-SOFC} S_{SOFC} N_{SOFC}$
Limit SOFC ramp-down rate	$-R_{rmp-SOFC} S_{SOFC} N_{SOFC} \leq e_{SOFC,t} - e_{SOFC,(t-1)}$
TES constraints	
Same initial & final SOC	$hw_{TES,0} = hw_{TES,8760}$
TES tank hot water balance	$hw_{TES,t} = hw_{TES,(t-1)} \alpha_{TES} + \eta_{TES_{ch}} hw_{ch-RES,t} - \frac{hw_{dch-RES,t}}{\eta_{TES_{dch}}}$
Limit the hot water level	$0 \leq hw_{TES,t} \leq \bar{\delta}_{TES}$
Building space heating and hot water heater equipment	
Heating output from GSH is limited by installed capacity	$g_{GSH,t} \leq \frac{S_{GSH} \Delta t}{\eta_{GSH}}$
Hot water from GWH is limited by installed capacity	$g_{GWH,t} \leq \frac{S_{GWH} \Delta t}{\eta_{GWH}}$
Heating output from ERSH is limited by installed capacity	$e_{ESH,t} \leq \frac{S_{ESH} \Delta t}{\eta_{ESH}}$
Hot water from ERWH is limited by installed capacity	$e_{EWH,t} \leq \frac{S_{EWH} \Delta t}{\eta_{EWH}}$

The objective function, decision variables, and constraints are developed in MATLAB R2014b [62] where toolboxes such as CPLEX Optimization Studio V12.8.0 [63] and YALMIP [64], [65] are used for an efficient and rapid solving of the linear mixed integer optimization problem.

4.3 Summary of model input and assumptions

The input data for techno-economic analysis, optimized design, and operation of a nanogrid residential system in CZ06 is presented in Table 4. The table includes the cost assumptions for 3 years: 2025, 2035, and 2045; the utility retail rates are assumed to be the values in each mid-decade. It is worth noting that the HP performance depends on the weather; the table shows the data for CZ06 where the water HP coefficient of performance (shown as η_{EWH}) is 2.46. While all the cost assumptions for CZ16 and ZC15 are similar, η_{EWH} of water HP in CZ16 and CZ15 are 1.65 and 2.65, respectively.

Table 4. Summary of input data and assumptions in DERopt model

Climate Zone	CZ6: LAX-UCI		(2025-2035)	(2035-2045)	(2045-2055)
Technology cost	PV (O&M=0.001(\$/kWh _e))		\$2484	\$1944	\$1317.5
	Battery (O&M=0.001(\$/kWh _e))		\$911.5	\$755	\$654
	SOFC (O&M=0.06 (\$/kWh _e))		\$5706	\$5529.5	\$5420.5
Retail rates For mid-decade	Import: RPS (%) cost adder (\$/kWh)		30% \$0.015/kWh	60% \$0.031 /kWh	100% \$0.054/kWh
	Export		NEM 2.0	NEM 3.0 (AC)	NEM 3.0 (AC)
	H ₂ fraction (by volume)		51%	86%	100%
	H ₂ cost		\$6/kg	\$4.5/kg	\$4/kg
	Cost of carbon		\$27.96/ton	\$50/ton	\$71.5/ton
Incentives	PV		MACRS:5 ITC: 1	MACRS: 0 ITC: 0	MACRS: 0 ITC: 0
	EES		MACRS:7 ITC: 0	MACRS: 0 ITC: 0	MACRS: 0 ITC: 0
	REES		MACRS:5 ITC: 1	MACRS: 0 ITC: 0	MACRS: 0 ITC: 0
	SOFC		TC: 30 %	TC: 30 %	TC: 30 %
Building Scenarios	1- Baseline (Appliance: gas)	Water Heater (η_{GWH})	Tank Gas (0.6)	Tank Gas (0.6)	Tank Gas (0.6)
		Space Heater (η_{GSH})	Gas (0.8)	Gas (0.8)	Gas (0.8)
	2- Premium Gas (Appliance: gas)	Water Heater (η_{GWH})	Condensing On-Demand Gas (0.96)	Condensing On-Demand Gas (0.96)	Condensing On-Demand Gas (0.96)
		Space Heater (η_{GSH})	Condensing Gas (0.96)	Condensing Gas (0.96)	Condensing Gas (0.96)
	3- Electric Resistive (Appliance: Electric)	Water Heater (η_{EWH})	Tank (0.9)	----	----
		Space Heater (η_{ESH})	Central Furnace (1.0)	----	----
	4- Premium Electric Resistive (Appliance: Electric)	Water Heater (η_{EWH})	On-Demand (η_{EWH})	----	----
		Space Heater (η_{ESH})	Central Furnace (1.0)	----	----
	5- Heat Pump (Appliance: Electric)	Water Heater (η_{EWH})	Hot Water HP (2.6)	Hot Water HP (2.6)	Hot Water HP (2.6)
		Space Heater (AFUE or SEER/HSPF)	Air-Source Heat Pump (14 / 8.2)	Air-Source Heat Pump (14 / 8.2)	Air-Source Heat Pump (14 / 8.2)
	6- Premium Heat Pump (Appliance: Electric)	Water Heater (η_{EWH})	Hot Water HP (2.6)	Hot Water HP (2.6)	Hot Water HP (2.6)
		Space Heater (AFUE or SEER/HSPF)	Mini-Split Ductless (29.3/14)	Mini-Split Ductless (29.3/14)	Mini-Split Ductless (29.3/14)

5 Results and Discussion

The aim of this techno-economic analysis and optimization is to investigate the impact of an SOFC mCHP on achieving California's ZNE goals in the residential sector. For a comprehensive study, we:

1. Examined each of the six building configurations for the three climate zones, establishing building energy cost and use prior to DER integration.
2. Identified and compared the annualized cost of the building energy that a house owner must pay for two cases: (1) ZNE constraint is implemented, (2) No ZNE constraint is applied. For both cases, the objective is to find the minimum cost of the nanogrid residence with the optimized design and operation of PV, battery, and SOFC, as well as utility purchases.
3. Broke down the total cost, component cost breakdown, annual TDV of primary energy import/export, annual energy components of the building, adopted technologies and their capacities are provided and compared.
4. Determined the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) for all DER technologies and utility service.
5. Performed a sensitivity analysis on sensitivity of results to different SOFC and H₂ cost.

Finally, examined dynamic operations of a ZNE building with different technology scenarios are presented for 2025, 2035, and 2045.

5.1 BEM Energy and Cost Prior to DER Integration

TDV energy and utility cost for the single-family residential BEM prior to DER integration is shown in Figure 4. This figure shows average TDV energy use from 2020 through 2050, as well as TDV energy use in 2025, 2035, and 2045. This figure also shows total cost of energy for 2025, 2035, and 2045 based on projected retail rates. Since no DER has been integrated, energy cost consists solely of electricity and gas utility bills. This figure shows utility cost increasing steadily for all heating system scenarios. Electric resistive systems are consistently the most expensive systems to power. Additionally, there is minimal difference in TDV energy use or cost between the standard and premium electric resistive scenarios.

This figure also shows a steady decline in TDV energy as both the electric grid and natural gas service is gradually decarbonized. Lowest TDV energy is achieved by the heat pump scenarios. Compared against the baseline, the premium heat pump scenario has lower TDV energy use by between 40% and 60% in moderate and warm climates (CZ06 and CZ16) and 60% to 75% in colder climates (CZ15).

Based on these results, electric resistive systems appear to be untenable from both cost and TDV energy use perspectives. Since electric resistive systems are still used in buildings throughout California, the 2025 analysis includes electric resistive systems. However, these results lead to an

assumption that electric resistive systems will be replaced across California by 2035. As a result, 2035 and 2045 analyses exclude electric resistive heating systems

Figure 5: Baseline TDV energy use and energy costs for the single-family residential building in CZ06, CZ15, and CZ16 for the six different building heating technology scenarios. TDV energy values include average, 2025, 2035, and 2045

5.2 Cost and Energy Characterization of ZNE vs. non-ZNE Buildings

The net annual cost of building energy in CZ06 with and without ZNE constraint are shown in Figure 5 (a) for the years 2025, 2035, and 2045. This cost is the sum of all annual utility gas and electricity bills, the amortized cost of equipment, and equipment O&M, minus NEM credits generated from electricity export. A TDV-based ZNE constraint considerably increases the cost of energy for the building owner for all scenarios. In the scenarios with gas heaters, ZNE constraint raised the cost by more than two times in 2025 and 2035. For the electrified houses the annual cost increased by 50%. To identify the reason for such a gap, cost breakdowns of each scenario with and without ZNE is shown in Figure 5 (b) and Figure 5 (c), respectively.

Comparing the cost components for each scenario with and without ZNE constraint, it is observed that ZNE houses cost much more than non-ZNE cases. The ZNE house is required to generate and export the equivalent amount of energy that it uses from the grid. The electricity from PV or REES could be exported to the grid. The PV exports electricity during inexpensive periods, while REES can store it and shift the electricity export to a more expensive time. A large portion of the cost in ZNE buildings belongs to REES which stores renewable electricity and exports it during peak hours. Grid-tied electricity storage systems adopted for ZNE buildings, EES, also result in higher annualized cost of these buildings.

The basis under which the homeowner is paid back for electricity export also affects the type and size of battery adoption. We can also see this in the bars on the left side of the Figure 5 (c) showing

the total price of selling electricity from PV and REES (PV-NEM and REES-NEM). In 2025, no battery was adopted for non-ZNE and only PV was used and exported electricity through NEM 2.0. However, in 2035 and 2045, the REES was deployed for non-ZNE cases to supply the building load and export electricity under the NEM 3.0. NEM 2.0 was introduced by California Public Utilities Commission (CPUC) to incentivize the PV owners by compensating for their PV export at full retail rates. In the updated version, NEM 3.0, PV export payments are reduced to the “avoided cost” to the utility which is much less than the retail rate and varies depending on the time of the export. NEM 3.0 encourages installing batteries with PVs to export more electricity during the peak hours when the grid needs it the most. Please refer to utility rate Section 3.3 for detailed description of NEM structures.

The income from PV-NEM (dark green bars) is limited in 2035 and 2045 versus 2025. Even though for non-ZNE cases there is no obligation under TDV arbitrage, REES is adopted to export electricity and benefit from the cost arbitrage under NEM 3.0. To visualize the effect of having a TDV based ZNE constraint, the annual TDV of energy transfers are presented in Figure 6.

Even though the utility cost of electricity is projected to increase in future, the annual cost of energy to the homeowner goes down for most technology scenarios. This is due to the combined effect of a reduction in PV and battery costs and the change in NEM structure. Though NEM 3.0 reduces the credit on extra solar export, it adds to the value of having battery energy storage for its load shifting capability.

Another significant difference between the ZNE and non-ZNE buildings is observed in 2045: SOFC technology is only adopted in 2045 while under a ZNE constraint. This means without a TDV-ZNE constraint, SOFC is not an economical option for a homeowner compared to other options such as the utility electricity, PV, and battery. Details on the capacity of purchased technologies are provided in section 5.3.

Figure 6. Total cost and cost breakdown of a building with ZNE vs. non-ZNE constraint – CZ06

The impact of having a TDV-ZNE constraint for a residential building in CZ06 could be explained by Figure 6. The summation of hourly TDV ($\text{kWh}_{\text{primary energy}} / \text{kWh}_{\text{imported energy}}$) of imported electricity (solid blue) and imported gas (solid orange) over a year are shown on the positive side of the axis; total TDV of primary energy saved by exporting electricity back to the grid in the same year is shown with the bars (hashed blue) on negative side. According to the TDV-ZNE definition, the total TDV of imported energy from electricity and gas grid must be offset by the total TDV of

exported electricity. As shown in Figure 6 (a), this is achieved for the building; however, without the TDV-ZNE constraint the summation of exported electricity TDV of is considerably lower than imported energy, Figure 6 (b).

No imported gas TDV is observed in 2045 even in the gas heating scenarios. This is due to the assumption that by 2045 the gas grid will be completely decarbonized. Importing 100% renewable gas does not need to be offset by exporting renewable electricity. The massive difference between the TDV of exported electricity in 2045 and 2025 shows the need for renewable gas in the gas infrastructure. As we move from 2025 towards 2045, the value of exported electricity to offset the gas import significantly decreases thanks to greater amount of decarbonized gas in the grids. Also, the electricity TDV intensity decreases over the years as more renewable electricity is integrated to the grid. This also results in lower values of blue bars in 2045 and 2035 compared to 2025.

The energy components of the building in kWh for both ZNE and non-ZNE cases are provided in Figure 7. Figure 7 (a) shows the total electricity demand of a ZNE house and the amount of electricity from different sources that are used to meet the demand for each technology scenario. The imported grid electricity and electricity from each DER system are shown by the bars on the positive side and the exported electricity by PV and REES on the left side of the axis.

Figure 7. TDV of energy transfer for a household with and without ZNE constraint-CZ06

The results with ZNE constraint show a few interesting points: in 2025, both electric resistive and heat pump technologies are considered for building electrification. The electric resistive heaters (both with tank and on-demand tankless) add much higher electricity load compared to heat pump. This encourages more investment in heat pumps to reduce their cost for residential applications. In the same year, for the scenarios with gas heating equipment, the total exported electricity is higher than the total building electricity demand. That’s due to the TDV-ZNE requirement to compensate for the fossil energy intensive gas consumption by exporting renewable electricity. Generally, in these cases the PV electricity is not used for the building demand and instead all of it is exported.

Another noteworthy point for ZNE buildings is the optimal use of batteries in all buildings. Except for electrified buildings in 2025, REES assets are adopted and used to absorb excess solar for eventual export during periods of high electric grid TDV energy intensity and/or high NEM export rates. The avoided cost export rate structure in NEM 3.0 encourages saving the grid electricity consumption during the peak hours (discharging EES to the building load) and instead sending electricity to the grid (discharging REES to the grid).

Last, but not least, is the significant role of SOFC in 2045 in providing the building demand and its role in achieving ZNE. Even though a renewable gas powered SOFC helps achieve a lower cost ZNE house in 2045, the electrified buildings achieve lowest cost. More details on how the EES and REES are charged/discharged and how SOFC helps ZNE is presented in dynamic operation results 5.7.

The energy components for the same scenarios without ZNE constraint are presented in Figure 7 (b). For all three years, the electricity demand of the non-ZNE houses is primarily met by the grid followed by PV. Though the cost components from Figure 5 (c) showed the adoption of REES in 2035 and 2045, Figure 7 (b) indicates that the electricity discharge from REES is mainly exported to the grid to benefit from the NEM 3.0 credits. With the NEM 2.0 in 2025, electricity export from PV is significantly higher compared to the PV export in 2035 and 2045 with NEM 3.0. NEM 2.0 is more favorable for solar adoption compared to NEM 3.0 which encourages adoption of storage systems.

(a) Annual electricity components for a house with ZNE constraint

Figure 8. Annual breakdown of energy components for a household-CZ06

5.3 Adopted DER technologies for ZNE vs. non-ZNE Buildings

DERopt finds the optimized design of DER sources to meet the building demand with the lowest cost. The optimized design and operation also tend to minimize the carbon emission due to direct and indirect costs associated with CO₂ emission in the model. The carbon costs (\$/ton) shown in Table 2 are directly included in cost of gas in each year. Also, since the ZNE constraint is based on TDV of energy (which is high during peak hours of fossil fuel consumption), saving energy during high TDV hours results in reducing carbon emissions. The adopted technologies and their installed capacities for each scenario of a ZNE building vs. non-ZNE is provided in Figure 8. The left axis is the installed battery capacity in (kWh) where green column bars represent the adopted REES and gray bars represent the EES. The right axis the power rating in (kW) with circle markers showing the purchased PV size and square marker representing the size of installed SOFC.

Figure 8 (a) shows the results for 2025 where the electricity export is under NEM 2.0 structure. As seen in Figure 5 (c), no battery is adopted when there is no obligation to reach ZNE in 2025 and only PV is installed. In contrast, the TDV-ZNE constraint made the model adopt large REES batteries. The PV size for gas appliances with ZNE constraint is significantly higher than non-ZNE cases.

In 2035, Figure 8 (b), we observe that batteries of about 10kWh capacity are the economical REES option for non-ZNE buildings. With TDV-ZNE constraint, both REES and EES are installed with a total capacity of 20-30 kWh for different scenarios. No SOFC is adopted in 2025 and 2035. In 2045, Figure 8 (c), a 0.5 kW SOFC is adopted for all scenarios of ZNE buildings at capital cost of $5420.5 \frac{\$}{\text{kWh}}$. It is assumed that in 2045 the gas is fully decarbonized with retail price of $4 \frac{\$}{\text{kgH}_2}$ which is equivalent to $3.93 \frac{\$}{\text{therm}}$. Without a ZNE constraint, SOFC is not a cost-effect option compared to a solar PV / battery system with supplemental utility support. SOFC m-CHP could be helpful for ZNE buildings because of its contribution to both electricity and hot water demand, and therefore reducing the energy import from the grid. More details are provided in dynamic result section 5.7. In the next section, we investigated the capital cost of SOFC at which it becomes competitive with other technologies when there is no ZNE constraint.

Figure 9. Adopted technologies and their optimized capacity a residential building-CZ06

5.4 SOFC capital cost to be an economical option for residential applications

The results from section 5.3 indicate that SOFC at its forecasted costs in 2025 (\$5706/kW), 2035 (\$5529.5/kW), and 2045 (\$5420.5/kW), is not competitive with other technologies for residential buildings when there is no ZNE requirement; even with 30% tax credit assumption in all years. To determine when SOFC technology does become competitive, we decreased equipment capital cost from its forecast values to determine the price at which the model picks SOFC in non-ZNE houses. For this, the retail rates of gas were kept constant, and only the SOFC cost was changed. Figure 9 illustrates the costs of SOFC where it becomes an economical choice for residential buildings in 2025 and 2035. The cost data for 2045 are presented in Figure 10.

For each building scenario, two bars are shown for SOFC cost: the purple bars are the forecasted SOFC cost, and the green bars are costs where a 0.5-kW SOFC was adopted. The costs shown with triangle markers are the total cost of building energy that a homeowner must pay in a year; these costs are comparable with the costs shown in Figure 5 (a) for non-ZNE houses.

The results show that in 2025, the SOFC becomes cost-effective when their prices are reduced from (\$5706/kW) to about (\$3000/kW). It is observed that SOFC capital cost must decrease the most under the “premium gas” and both heat pump scenarios. In scenarios with electric resistive heaters, ERH and premium ERH, SOFC was adopted at higher costs \$4500-5000/kW_e.

Figure 10. SOFC price to be cost-economic for a non-ZNE house - CZ06

In 2035, the SOFC price must be reduced further down to compete with other DER sources such as PV and battery. In all scenarios the SOFC capital cost must be lowered to \$2000/kW or lower

to be an economical DER option. For a less efficient heating technology, baseline gas heaters, it is economical at a slightly higher price.

In 2045, with H₂ at \$4/kg, the optimization model did not pick SOFC for non-ZNE buildings even when its price was reduced to zero. So, the H₂ cost was reduced to find a cost point at which a renewable gas powered SOFC gets adopted. The results are provided in Figure 10. The right axis shows the H₂ cost (\$/kW) with purple bar as the forecasted price in 2045 and green bars for economic H₂ cost in 2045. The left axis shows the cost (\$) with cross markers representing the economic SOFC capital cost and the circle markers representing the annual cost of energy for a building with SOFC and H₂ at those costs. These annual costs could be compared with values shown by triangle markers that represent the total cost with H₂ at \$4/kg (hence with no SOFC).

Figure 11. H₂ and SOFC price as a cost-effective option non-ZNE house in 2045 - CZ06

In this set of analyses the SOFC tax credit was lowered from 30% to 10% to get a realistic idea of its cost competitiveness compared to other technologies. At \$1400/kW, SOFC was adopted in baseline scenario. In the other 3 scenarios, it was not adopted unless its capital cost was reduced to \$1000/kW and the H₂ gas price delivered to the households was lowered to \$1/kg.

5.5 Levelized Cost of Energy and Storage for ZNE vs. non-ZNE residential buildings

For a fair comparison of different energy generation technologies in each year and scenario, the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) and levelized cost of storage (LCOS) are assessed. LCOE for each technology is simply calculated by dividing the sum of the amortized equipment, O&M, and fuel costs by annual electricity output. LCOS is calculated similarly, except that electricity output is replaced with the sum of discharged electricity. The results for residential building with and without ZNE constraint are provided in Figure 11 (a) and Figure 11 (b), respectively. All the data for gas and equipment costs are the same as the ones provided in Table 2 except for the non-ZNE cases that SOFC are not adopted at those predicted costs. So, for SOFC in non-ZNE cases, the

price points where it is adopted, shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10 are used in calculations of SOFC LCOE.

Figure 12. LCOE and LCOS for alternative sources – CZ06

The total LCOE, black bars, is the value of objective function divided by the total electric load. The first notable point is the difference between the Total LCOE in ZNE buildings and their corresponding non-ZNE scenarios. With ZNE constraint, the total electricity LCOE is more than double the non-ZNE case. Therefore, for the non-ZNE houses, the cost of SOFC had to be reduced from the forecast prices to be economically feasible. Going from 2025 towards 2045, the total electricity LCOE decreases for each scenario regardless of an increase in utility LCOE. For solar PV LCOE, the price of exporting PV is subtracted from its capital and O&M cost to find the net PV cost. It has the lowest LCOE among all technologies in most of the scenarios which is why it is hard for SOFC to compete. Note that despite the low price of PV, it is not enough to achieve ZNE just by installing PV even at a very large capacity due to its intermittent and limited availability. It must be complemented with other technologies such as storage and SOFC, which can continuously operate.

REES LCOS includes export under NEM 2.0 and 3.0 rates. Thus Storage LCOS values in 2035 and 2045 are negative because the value of electricity export by REES equipment costs. Under the

ZNE constraints, REES export is managed to maximize the offset primary energy. However, under the non-ZNE scenario, REES export is exclusively focused on lowering cost. As a result, REES export occurs strategically when export value is highest.

Dynamic operation results shown in Section 5.7 also show EES systems being used to perform demand shifting (i.e., absorbing excess solar or utility import when electric TDV intensity is low, followed by discharge in non-solar hours when electric TDV intensity or utility costs are high). Storage shifting LCOS is the cost of generating 1 kWh of electricity by PV, storing it in battery and discharging it at night. Under ZNE scenarios, this battery storage strategy is a key method for reducing TDV intensity in non-solar hours. The decrease of storage shifting cost from 2035 to 2045 is due to the lower cost of batteries and lower avoided cost of electricity in 2045 compared to 2035 (flatter TVD profile). Analysis excluding a SOFC option shows that this strategy is deployed extensively to achieve ZNE. LCOS under this scenario is higher than the LCOE of SOFC operation, explaining why SOFC adoption occurs under ZNE scenarios.

5.6 Sensitivity of annualized energy cost to SOFC and fuel costs

In the last part of techno-economic analysis for ZNE buildings, a sensitivity analysis is conducted to evaluate the sensitivity of the total energy cost of a ZNE building to the capital cost of SOFC. These sensitivity analyses are different from the analyses in section 5.4 which were performed to find an economical cost of SOFC for non-ZNE buildings. The results for 2045 and 2035 are provided in Figure 12 and Figure 13, respectively. No sensitivity analysis is done for 2025 as the SOFC was not adopted with ZNE constraint.

As shown in Figure 12, the annual cost of building energy has a linear relation with SOFC capital cost with the same slope for all scenarios. In the electrified scenario with HP (blue cross markers) at capital costs lower than \$2000/kW, two units of SOFCs were adopted by the model which also resulted in a different slope. In these set of simulations, the tax credit assumption for SOFC was zero ($SOFC_{TC}=0$). In 2045, the SOFC cost was reduced from \$4500/kW to \$1000/kW by an increment of \$500. The results show that reduction of SOFC price by \$500/kW, resulted in \$104 reduction of annual energy cost to the homeowner.

Figure 13. Sensitivity of total energy cost of a ZNE building to the SOFC cost in 2045

In 2035, the 30% tax credit assumption for SOFC was maintained to increase its cost-effectiveness to be adopted by DERopt. Figure 13 shows that for all scenarios except for baseline gas heater (red circle markers), the annual energy cost is remained unchanged by SOFC cost reduction. This is because the model did not adopt SOFC at those costs and the changing SOFC price did not affect the annual cost. Reducing \$500 in SOFC cost resulted in \$82 reduction in total cost of baseline scenario. SOFC was adopted at \$2000/kW and \$1500/kW in premium gas and electrified scenarios, respectively.

Figure 14. Sensitivity of total energy cost of a ZNE building to the SOFC cost in 2035

5.7 Optimal DER Operation and Dynamic Results

In this section, the optimized operation of different energy technologies in a ZNE house is provided. The annual dispatch is on an hourly basis; for each hour DERopt determines equipment operation that achieves lowest total cost of energy while meeting building energy loads. Since the ZNE constraint is based on TDV of primary energy, the optimization model respond to TDV signals. So, the model provides an optimal citizen behavior which can respond strongly by replacing early evening utility electricity with renewable energy via solar PV and storage when peaker plant operation is most likely to occur. This is in contrast to midday operation when low cost electricity with relatively low TDV electricity is available.

The dynamic results are presented in the following order to point out the main findings; in the first subsection, a winter week in 2035 (where the optimizer did not adopt SOFC) and 2045 (DERopt optimizer adopted SOFC) are selected to show how having an SOFC can affect the operation of different components. The results show the dynamics of SOFC, PV, EES, REES, and utility to meet the electric and hot water loads. In this part, only one scenario is selected to avoid redundancy (scenario 6 where building is electrified with premium heat pump). Next, the performance of all building scenarios in each year is provided for a winter and summer week to see the impact of different heating technologies.

5.7.1 Dynamic results in 2035 (without SOFC) and 2045 (with SOFC)

Figure 14 shows the dynamic operation of different energy resources to meet the electric demand of a ZNE building in a winter week. The building is electrified with premium HP for space heating and hot water demands (scenario 6). The major gridlines on the x-axis correspond to noon each day. Dates are selected such that both weeks start on Sunday.

The heating appliances in this case are the premium HP. So, the total electric load, shown with black dotted line, is the summation of the electricity demand for hot water HP, electricity demand to charge the EES, and the general building electricity demand which is shown with black solid line and includes space heating, cooling, lights, miscellaneous plugs, etc. The difference between the solid black and green line is the electricity charged by EES. The difference between the solid green line and the dotted black line is the electricity demand by the hot water HP.

Both in 2035 and 2045, sharp spikes are observed every day in the early hours of the afternoon (on the right side of major gridlines). This is the imported electricity from the grid, shown in light blue, to charge the EES. The navy areas represent part of the building load that is supplied by EES. So, every day, the EES is charged by the grid during the off-peak hours and is discharged to the building within a few hours of peak price. The spikes occur because batteries are charged in a short time during the last hours of off-peak period instead of smooth charging over all off-peak hours. This feature is due to the batteries self-discharge physics that is captured by DERopt (refer to battery energy balance constraint available in Table 3). The optimized charging time to avoid the self-discharge penalty is found to be just before the peak hours. The difference between the magnitude of EES charging power in 2035 (more than 6 kW) and 2045 (less than 3 kW) is due to the larger size of batteries installed in 2035; compare the installed capacity of EES for ZNE cases in Figure 8 section (b) and (c).

The red areas are the part of the electric load directly supplied by solar PV, usually before noon (left side of the gridlines). Figure 14 (a) shows that in 2035 the electricity demand is supplied by the grid, EES (peak hours), and PV (off-peak hours). In 2045, Figure 14 (b), the SOFC is adopted and is mostly running at its rated power (0.5 kW). During midday when there is solar generation, the SOFC switches to part-load (half the installed capacity: 0.25kW) and remains hot. It is observed that SOFC provides a great amount of building baseload which is the reason for smaller battery capacities and utility imports in 2045.

Figure 15. Electricity dynamics of an electrified ZNE building in winter

Figure 15 (a) and (b) illustrate the battery charging and discharging dynamics both for grid tied (EES) and renewable (REES) storage systems in the same winter weeks of 2035 and 2045,

respectively. The solar generation profile for the same weeks is also provided; the red areas show part of the solar power directly used by the building, the yellow areas show the PV power stored in REES, and the orange areas represent the exported PV power to the grid which are shown as negative values.

For a better understanding of dispatch profiles in both EES and REES, the corresponding TDV factors ($\text{kWh}_{\text{primary energy}}/\text{kWh}_{\text{electricity}}$) in each year are added to the plots with magenta line. Note that the TDV factors are close to zero during midday when the solar generation is high. During the off-peak hours that the societal costs of energy increases and energy saving becomes very valuable, the TDV factors rise to about 1.5 ($\text{kWh}_{\text{primary energy}}/\text{kWh}_{\text{electricity}}$) in 2035, Figure 15(a) and to 1 ($\text{kWh}_{\text{primary energy}}/\text{kWh}_{\text{electricity}}$) in 2045, Figure 15(b). With the TDV based ZNE constraint, provided in Table 3, the value of imported energy at each hour is multiplied by its corresponding TDV factor; at the end of the year, the total value of the used primary energy ($\text{kWh}_{\text{primary energy}}$) must be offset by the total value of exported energy. This value is the sum product of the exported electricity ($\text{kWh}_{\text{electricity}}$) and its corresponding TDV factor ($\text{kWh}_{\text{primary energy}}/\text{kWh}_{\text{electricity}}$).

The optimization model pushes the battery discharge closer to the times with higher TDV values. For EES, the light blue areas that show the grid electricity import to charge the battery appear when the TDV factors are zero. The navy areas which show the EES discharge to the building coincide with the higher values of TDV to save the primary energy consumption during the peak hours. Note that the EES is charged immediately before it is discharged to prevent its self-discharge from noon to the start of peak hours.

The electricity stored in EES is not discharged to the grid; only the PV electricity is exported to the grid either directly during the day (orange areas) or indirectly through REES (dark green areas). As expected, the electricity from REES is not exported in the middle of the day when there is plenty of solar available in the grid and both electricity price and energy intensity is low; Instead, it is stored in REES and is sold to the grid when the TDV or avoided cost is higher.

As seen for the EES discharge time, the REES shifts the electricity discharge towards the time with higher TDV factors and avoided costs. Electricity export during this time is beneficial both for the utility and homeowner; utility can purchase clean electricity during peak hours from decentralized energy resources instead of operating fossil energy intensive peaker power plants with higher emissions. On the other hand, the homeowner earns higher credit by selling the electricity when the energy value is high. This is a good citizen behavior; not only the grid electricity is saved by discharging EES to meet the building demand, but also renewable electricity is exported to the grid at the same time to help the electricity shortage.

The higher amounts of REES electricity export in 2035 compared to 2045 is due to the larger REES installed in 2035, as shown in Figure 8. The REES discharge to the building is designated with light green as REES in Figure 14 and as REES-D in Figure 15. It is worth noting that during this time, REES was never used for the building demand, and it was all exported to the grid. At the same time, EES was discharged to the building to save the electricity import from the grid and avoid higher costs of electricity during peak hours.

Figure 16. Dynamics of batteries, PV, and grid electricity interactions in winter

Battery state of charge (SOC) in the same winter week of 2035 and 2045 is plotted in Figure 16 (a) and (b), respectively. The green line belongs to the REES and the black line belongs to the EES. The minimum SOC of both EES and REES is 10%; it is observed that both batteries charge/discharge once a day. REES starts charging before noon and it follows the solar generation profile while the EES starts charging in the afternoons. Both batteries are discharged within a short period of peak hours instead of discharging over the entire night.

The DERopt model is designed based on a price structure that is predicted in the future. Import and export rates are assumed to be constant, regardless of DER adoption and operation (i.e., DERopt is a price taker model); it is not designed to make prices and market based on the customers' behavior. If all households start to discharge their batteries at the same time during the peak hours, the high value of saving electricity and avoided cost at that hour will shift to a later hour when the batteries are empty, and the grid electricity must be imported. Since NEM 3.0 rates are based on wholesale electricity prices, optimal battery dispatch may result in wholesale rate shapes changing each night as utilities responded to optimal ratepayer battery dispatch from the prior night. Overall, this is likely to discourage REES adoption due to lack of consistent foresight

to what NEM 3.0 rates will look like day to day, or to the subsidization of REES owners.

Figure 17. Dynamics of battery state of charge in winter

Last dynamic result in this section shows the DHW demand of the building in the same winter week of 2035, Figure 17 (a), and 2045, Figure 17 (b). In 2035, no SOFC is installed and therefore only electricity is used for DHW. Since the results belong to scenario 6 where premium HP with a high average COP (2.4) is used, the consumed electricity (blue area) is less than the DHW demand (black line). In 2045, SOFC is adopted, and accordingly thermal energy storage (TES) is used to store the SOFC cogenerated domestic hot water for future use. The SOFC hot water is either directly used for DHW (lilac area) or is indirectly used by first being stored in TES and then discharged (red area) when needed. If the DHW demand is more than available hot water, then electricity is used to power the HP (blue area).

Figure 18. Dynamics of domestic hot water (DHW) demand in winter

5.7.2 Building dynamics and energy breakdown under different heating scenarios

In this section, the electric load of the building under different heating technologies are presented. Results for 2025, 2035, and 2045 are shown in Figure 18, Figure 19, and Figure 20, respectively. For each year, the dynamic results of one summer week (the left plots) and one winter week (the right plots) are shown. In addition, an annual breakdown of different energy resources to supply the total electric demand is provided in a pie chart.

Figure 18 shows the results for six scenarios of heating technology that are introduced in building equipment scenario section 2.2. The scenarios in 2025 are: (a) baseline gas: gas heater with tank, (b) premium gas: tankless on-demand gas heater, (c) electric resistive heater (ERH) with hot water storage tank, (d) premium ERH with a tankless on demand water heater, (e) heat pump (ducted air

source HP), and (f) premium heat pump (ductless mini-split HP). For the gas appliance scenarios, Figure 18 (a) and (b), the electric load only includes the electricity demand for the building and charging EES. The dynamic result shows that most of the demand is met by the grid; EES is charged in the last hours of off-peak time and is immediately discharged for a few hours in the peak hours until fully discharged (reached their allowed DoD). The corresponding pie charts indicate that in these 2 scenarios, grid constitutes more than 60% of the electric demand (directly) and the rest is only supplied by the grid-tied storage, EES (indirectly supplied by the grid). Though PV and REES are installed in these scenarios, as shown in Figure 5 (a) and Figure 8 (a), they don't supply the building load. PV is not used for the building demand; its electricity is either sold to the grid under NEM 2.0 or is stored in REES and later sold to the grid to avoid higher costs.

The electric scenarios in 2025 includes both resistive heaters and heat pumps. So, the total electric load is higher than previous cases because of the additional electricity demand for space heaters. The added electric load depends on the heater efficiency which is available in Table 2. The pie charts in ERH scenarios, Figure 18 (c) and (d), show that 50% of the electric demand is covered by the grid, 27% directly from PV, and 23% by REES (indirectly from PV). The results are different from the gas scenarios; no EES was installed (seen in Figure 8 (a)) or used, PV power is directly used by the building (red area) specially during the summer days. The REES discharges electricity to the building (light green area) shortly after sunset.

This behavior is also observed for both heat pump scenarios in Figure 18 (e) and (f). The difference between HP and ERH scenarios is the lower electric load of space heaters in HPs which is more noticeable in winter weeks (left charts). The electricity sources used for the building are also the same as ERH with a different share of each element (lower grid and higher PV and REES).

Figure 19. Electricity dynamics in winter (left) and summer (right) + annual breakdowns -2025

Figure 19 shows the corresponding results in 2035 where only HPs are used for the electrified buildings (assuming that ERHs will be replaced by efficient HPs in the market) and there are four building scenarios 1,2,5, and 6: (a) baseline, (b) premium gas, (c) HP, and (d) premium HP. According to Figure 8 (b), EES, REES, and PV are installed for all scenarios at different sizes. In all scenarios the pie charts indicate that the building electric load is supplied by grid, EES, and PV. Unlike the electrified scenarios in 2025, where part of the REES electricity was discharged to the buildings, in 2035, all REES electricity is exported to the grid, and nothing is discharged to the building. This is attributed to the fact that the export structure is NEM 2.0 in 2025 and NEM 3.0 in 2035. Under NEM 3.0, the avoided cost from exporting electricity during the peak hours in evening is higher than midday which encourages electricity export in the evening. The sharp spikes in grid electricity import just before the EES discharge in peak hours is used to charge the EES.

Figure 20. Electricity dynamics in winter (left) and summer (right) + annual breakdowns - 2035

Finally, Figure 20 illustrates how an SOFC helps a residential building achieve ZNE in 2045. The four scenarios are similar to 2035. In the gas heater scenarios, a 0.5-kW SOFC was able to provide 50% of building electricity demand and the other 50% is supplied by grid, PV, and EES. Figure

20 (c) and (d) prove that installing an SOFC is also an optimized decision for electrified ZNE buildings even though the total electric demand is higher than the non-electrified buildings. The capacity factor of SOFC is the annual average energy production divided by its total energy production when it operates at rated capacity for every hour of the year. In all scenarios, the SOFC operated with a capacity factor of 0.76.

In 2045, the gas infrastructure is assumed to be 100% renewable; so, the imported gas for SOFC does not require to be offset by the building. So, SOFC can help achieve ZNE houses only if the gas is already decarbonized. Addition of SOFC resulted in a significant reduction in the size of EES, REES, and PV in ZNE buildings. The results of annual building energy cost in Figure 5 (b) also confirmed that in 2045, installing the SOFC at 5420.5(\$/kW) was the most cost-effective way to achieve ZNE.

Figure 21. Electricity dynamics in winter (left) and summer (right) + annual breakdowns -2045

In addition to supplying the electricity demand, an mCHP SOFC can provide part of the DHW needs. Figure 21 indicates the contribution of each source to supply the total DHW demand of

2573 kWh in all scenarios of 2045. The hot water is either directly used from SOFC or is stored in TES tank for later usage; the figures show that together they cover 60% of DHW demand. In 2045, gas or electricity consumption for the water heaters falls to 40% from 2035 and 2045.

Figure 22. Contribution of resources to annual DHW demand for a ZNE home -2045

5.8 Investigation of ZNE houses in other California climate zones

In this section, some of the results from CZ06 (along the Pacific Ocean) with mild weather are compared with two other cities in SoCalGas territory in different climate zones and different building loads. Brawley in CZ15 (low desert) has high cooling demand during extremely hot and dry summers (high electric load). Bishop in CZ16 (mountainous and semiarid region) has high heating loads during winter [66]. The same set of optimizations were performed for a ZNE building in CZ15 and CZ16.

Figure 22 shows the net annual cost of energy for a ZNE homeowner in (a) CZ15, (b) CZ06, and (c) CZ16. Both CZs require higher costs than CZ06 to achieve ZNE. However, the general trend of results in all three CZs are consistent. In 2045, SOFC is adopted both in CZ16 and CZ15. This indicates that SOFC helps achieve ZNE home in California even for extreme CZs with high heating or cooling load. In CZ16, the total cost of energy in 2025 and 2035 is significantly higher due to REES and EES costs. The high heating demand in CZ16 requires higher gas/electricity consumption which must be offset. Going from 2025 to 2045, even though the retail rate of gas increases, the net annual energy cost of ZNE building decreases. This is due to the presence of more renewable gas in the grid which does not require to be offset in ZNE calculations.

Figure 23. Comparison of annualized energy cost for a ZNE home in 3 CZs of California

The total value of primary energy consumption in each CZ (annual TDV of imported energy in kWh_{primary energy}) is provided in Figure 23. The yearly value of imported gas in Figure 23 (c) for gas heating scenarios is significantly higher compared to CZ06 and CZ15 due to high heating demands of CZ16. The orange bars are particularly longer in 2025 which highlights the need for

decarbonized gas in grids to fulfil the ZNE goals. The relatively large solid blue bars of CZ15 even in 2045 is due to its high electricity consumption for cooling loads in summer.

The total electricity consumptions of each CZ over selected the years are shown in Figure 24. The blue bars representing the imported electricity are persistently higher in Figure 24 (a) CZ15 compared to Figure 24 (b) CZ06 due to higher cooling demands. In Figure 24 (c) CZ16, however, the electrified buildings with electric resistive heaters (ERH) import significantly more electricity. In CZ16, even though the heat pumps have lower performance compared to CZ15 and CZ06, as explained in building energy modelling section, 2.2 (COP of 1.45 vs. 2.5), they substantially reduced the electricity consumption in electrified buildings. This emphasizes the need for more R&D and investment in commercialization and deployment of space heat pumps in colder regions.

Figure 24. Comparison of annual TDV of energy transfer for a ZNE home in 3 CZs of California

In all CZs of Figure 24, SOFC contributes to the electricity demand in 2045. For all three zones under study, only one SOFC of 0.5-kW was adopted. In Figure 24 (a) CZ15, even though the imported electricity in 2045 is much higher than the contribution of SOFC, the optimization model only adopted one SOFC instead of two. Since we assumed that the SOFC is a 500-Watt unit as an integer variable, adopting two SOFC units was found to be oversized and economically unreasonable for CZ15. When the optimization was performed assuming SOFC as a scalable unit

and continuous variable, an SOFC with 800-watt capacity was found to be an optimal size.

Figure 25. Annual breakdown of energy components in a ZNE home in California

Figure 25 provides a comparison of the total energy cost of a ZNE vs. non-ZNE building in (a) CZ15, (b) CZ06, (c) CZ16. The overall trend in price change is consistent among all CZs; the

values, however, are significantly higher in CZ16. The gap between the ZNE and non-ZNE costs are larger for gas scenarios compared electrified buildings. This gap decreases over the years from 2025 to 2045 thanks to higher amount of decarbonized gas in the infrastructure.

Optimized technologies and their capacity for buildings in CZ15 and CZ16 are provided in Figure 26 and Figure 27, respectively. Overall, the type of energy technologies for each year is consistent among all CZs. For instance, no battery is used for CZ15 and CZ16 in 2025 for non-ZNE buildings as shown for CZ06 in Figure 8 (a) too. In 2035 and 2045, only REES is adopted for non-ZNE buildings in all climate zones. Similar to ZNE buildings in CZ06, the capacity of installed technologies for ZNE buildings in CZ15 and CZ16 are substantially larger than non-ZNE cases and this difference is at its highest in 2025.

(a) Annual energy cost to a homeowner in California - CZ15

(b) Annual energy cost to a homeowner in California - CZ06

(c) Annual energy cost to a homeowner in California - CZ16

Figure 26. Comparison of annual energy cost for a building with and without ZNE constraint

Figure 27. Adopted technologies and their optimized capacity in CZ15

Figure 28. Adopted technologies and their optimized capacity in CZ16

6 Summary & Conclusions

Techno-economic analysis and optimized hourly operation of ZNE residential buildings in California are provided using a Distributed Energy Resource optimization tool (DERopt). DERopt uses Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) to find the optimized type, size, and operation of energy technologies such as rooftop PV, battery energy storage, SOFC mCHP, and thermal energy storage to achieve ZNE at minimum cost. The building is interconnected with both electricity and gas grid to evaluate how different heating appliance scenarios (electrified and gas heaters) impact feasibility of a ZNE residential building.

In this study, three California climate zones spanning the 16 CEC zones are selected for detailed analysis: CZ06 (mild heating and cooling loads), CZ15 (hot summers with high cooling load), and CZ16 (cold winter with high heating load). The heating and electric loads of a single-family housing are obtained from BEopt building energy modeling tool for six scenarios of heating appliances using gas or electricity (electric resistive, heat pumps). Techno-economic analysis of the ZNE building is conducted with realistic electricity and gas retail rates in California, as well as capital cost projections of PV, batteries, and SOFC in 2025, 2035, and 2045. The TDV of energy developed by California Energy Commission to support Title 24 evolution is used to define in ZNE.

Key findings of these analyses are summarized here:

- High TDV factors means the operation of inefficient and polluting peaker power plants because of high electricity demand, high carbon emission, high electricity price, and in general, high societal cost of energy. Setting a TDV-based ZNE as one of the constraints for the cost minimization function helps both the utility and the homeowner save energy during these peak hours with high TDV. TDV signals control the dispatch of electricity resources and batteries such that the building operates as a good citizen.
- With California's projected hourly TDVs, a good citizen is encouraged to use the grid electricity during the day when TDV is low (electricity is ample, cheap, and low emission due to high solar availability) and to save or export electricity when TDV is high. During the peak hours, the grid has a hard time supplying all the electric loads, so a good citizen can help the utility either by exporting electricity to the grid or by consuming the charged electricity in the batteries (self-consumption). DERopt provided the optimal operational decisions to minimize the energy costs for the homeowner while helping the grid when it needs electricity.
- Since SOFC mCHP can generate electricity continuously throughout the day on the building site, and its co-generated heat can be used for domestic hot water demands, it can play a role in decarbonizing the residential buildings and their self-consumption.
- With the current cost projections for SOFC, it is an economical energy choice for residential buildings only if there is a ZNE constraint; without a ZNE constraint, the optimization model did not adopt SOFC at all. In fact, the sensitivity analyses showed that the capital and operational of SOFC must be substantially reduced in the next years to compete with other technologies for residential applications such PV and batteries.

- Under a ZNE constraint, the use of any non-renewable resource increases energy use that must be offset by export from onsite solar production. Under this constraint, using non-renewable fuel in a SOFC increases the amount of energy that must be offset to achieve ZNE. Optimization results indicate that any potential value created by using non-renewable fuel in a SOFC is offset by the cost incurred to offset the higher energy use. As a result, the SOFC is economically preferred only when using 100% renewable fuel.
- The results highlight the significance of having 100% renewable gas in the gas grid which does not require to be offset by renewable electricity export from a ZNE building.
- Even though a renewable gas powered SOFC helps achieve an optimized ZNE home in 2045, comparison between the gas and electric heating appliance shows that the building still needs to be first electrified with efficient heat pumps to achieve the lowest cost and energy consumption.
- Comparing the ZNE and non-ZNE scenarios, ZNE requirement always increases the cost of energy to a homeowner. Optimizing DER resources for the non-ZNE scenario selects resources based on lowest cost alone. Under a ZNE constraint, the fossil energy content of non-renewable electricity and natural gas must be offset by export from onsite renewables. As a result, conventional energy sources carry an additional cost burden associated with increasing onsite solar capacity that offsets higher energy use. As a result, optimal ZNE designs tend to require larger solar PV and battery systems, and a SOFC powered using renewable fuel.
- Under non-ZNE scenarios, SOFC systems are found to be uneconomical at current projected equipment and fuel costs. Sensitivity analyses showed that both SOFC equipment and fuel costs must decrease if economic adoption is to occur: SOFC equipment cost must decrease from \$5,000 to \$1,000 per kW (80% reduction) while H₂ cost must drop to \$1 per kg.
- Despite the rise of utility costs for electricity in the future, it is observed that the net annual cost of energy to the homeowner goes down. This is attributed to the followings: reduced capital cost of PV and battery in future, optimized decisions made by the model (DERopt) on when to import/export electricity from/to the grid, and when to charge/discharge the batteries to achieve the lowest costs.
- The hourly charge/discharge profile of renewable energy storage system (REES) shows that the electricity from REES is not exported in the middle of the day when there is plenty of solar available in the grid and the price is low; Instead, it is stored in REES and is sold to the grid at higher price later in the day when the grid needs it the most (i.e., when the TDV factors or avoided costs are higher).
- The hourly dispatch profile of grid-tied energy storage system (EES) shows that the grid electricity is used to charge EES during the final off-peak hours of the day to minimize the energy loss from battery self-discharge. EES is daily charged from the grid at low cost and is only discharged to the building during the peak hours until reaching the depth of discharge.

The work shows that a SOFC powered with renewable H₂ is cost competitive versus a solar and battery system designed to provide energy throughout all hours of the day. This suggests that the SOFC system can be valuable at current prices for improving grid resiliency and reliability in regions plagued with regular outages. This work additionally did not consider scenarios where both an outage occurred over a period of prolonged adverse weather, reducing total solar yield. This application is worth exploring as a means of 1) developing low cost, highly resilient energy systems, and 2) encouraging SOFC manufacturing, possibly reducing equipment cost for all applications. This suggested additional research should also include consideration of a larger fuel cell system powering multiple buildings or distribution circuits in a microgrid configuration, enabling improved economies of scale.

The final major outcome from this work is that the current residential fuel cell sizes appear to be oversized for the residential application. Residential SOFC systems are available in 1.5 kW increments. Our work repeatedly showed that, when adopted, SOFC systems at 0.5 kW are preferable. In these instances, considering a 1.5 kW system leads to reduced system adoption and a preference for solar and battery systems. Our simulation results show that smaller SOFC systems must be available to enable economic adoption.

7 References

- [1] California Energy Commission, *2019 Building Energy Efficiency Standards for Residential and Nonresidential Buildings - Title 24*. 2019.
- [2] J. Freeman, "System Advisor Model (SAM)," *National Renewable Energy Laboratory*, 2018. .
- [3] N. Blair *et al.*, "System Advisor Model (SAM) General Description," Golden, CO, 2018.
- [4] C. Mohammed *et al.*, "Extended method for the sizing, energy management, and techno-economic optimization of autonomous solar Photovoltaic/Battery systems: Experimental validation and analysis," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 270, no. September, p. 116267, 2022.
- [5] E. Gul *et al.*, "A techno-economic analysis of a solar PV and DC battery storage system for a community energy sharing," *Energy*, vol. 244, p. 123191, 2022.
- [6] N. DiOrio, A. Dobos, and S. Janzou, "Economic Analysis Case Studies of Battery Energy Storage with SAM," 2015.
- [7] L. Martín-Pomares, D. Martínez, J. Polo, D. Perez-Astudillo, D. Bachour, and A. Sanfilippo, "Analysis of the long-term solar potential for electricity generation in Qatar," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 73, no. January, pp. 1231–1246, 2017.
- [8] Y. Zhang, A. Lundblad, P. E. Campana, F. Benavente, and J. Yan, "Battery sizing and rule-based operation of grid-connected photovoltaic-battery system: A case study in Sweden," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 133, pp. 249–263, 2017.
- [9] C. Li, "Economic and performance evaluation of grid-connected residential solar photovoltaic systems in Northwest China," *Energy Sources, Part A Recover. Util. Environ. Eff.*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 5473–5489, 2022.
- [10] G. S. Georgiou, P. Christodoulides, and S. A. Kalogirou, "Optimizing the energy storage schedule of a battery in a PV grid-connected nZEB using linear programming," *Energy*, vol. 208, p. 118177, 2020.
- [11] K. Heine, A. Thatte, and P. C. Tabares-Velasco, "A simulation approach to sizing batteries for integration with net-zero energy residential buildings," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 139, pp. 176–185, 2019.
- [12] "HOMER Energy," *HOMER*. .
- [13] S. Park, Y. Jang, and E. Kim, "Multi-objective optimization for sizing multi-source renewable energy systems in the community center of a residential apartment complex," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 244, no. June, p. 114446, 2021.
- [14] J. Liu *et al.*, "Techno-economic design optimization of hybrid renewable energy applications for high-rise residential buildings," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 213, no. April, p. 112868, 2020.
- [15] "JEPlus," *JEPlus - An parametric tool for EnergyPlus and TRNSYS*. .
- [16] C. Luerssen, O. Gandhi, T. Reindl, C. Sekhar, and D. Cheong, "Life cycle cost analysis (LCCA) of PV-powered cooling systems with thermal energy and battery storage for off-grid applications," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 273, no. April, p. 115145, 2020.
- [17] M. Wetter, "Generic Optimization Program." Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, Berkeley, California.
- [18] T. M. I. Riayatsyah, T. A. Geumpana, I. M. R. Fattah, S. Rizal, and T. M. I. Mahlia, "Techno-Economic Analysis and Optimisation of Campus Grid-Connected Hybrid Renewable Energy System Using HOMER Grid," *Sustainability*, no. Special Issue Solar Energy Utilization and Sustainable Development, 2022.
- [19] L. Novoa, R. Flores, and J. Brouwer, "Optimal renewable generation and battery storage sizing and siting considering local transformer limits," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 256, no. October, p. 113926, 2019.
- [20] R. J. Flores and J. Brouwer, "Optimal design of a distributed energy resource system that economically reduces carbon emissions," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 232, no. September, pp. 119–138, 2018.
- [21] R. J. Flores, "Costs and Operating Dynamics of Integrating Distributed Energy Resources in Commercial and Industrial Buildings with Electric Vehicle Charging [DISSERTATION]," 2016.
- [22] R. Flores and J. Brouwer, "Optimal Design of a Distributed Energy Resources System That Minimizes Cost While Reducing Carbon Emissions," *ASME 2017 11th Int. Conf. Energy Sustain.*, 2017.

- [23] L. Novoa, R. Flores, and J. Brouwer, "International Journal of Electrical Power and Energy Systems Optimal DER allocation in meshed microgrids with grid constraints," *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 128, no. January, p. 106789, 2021.
- [24] M. Califano, M. Sorrentino, M. A. Rosen, and C. Pianese, "Optimal heat and power management of a reversible solid oxide cell based microgrid for effective technoeconomic hydrogen consumption," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 319, no. May, p. 119268, 2022.
- [25] T. Khan, M. Yu, and M. Waseem, "Review on recent optimization strategies for hybrid renewable energy system with hydrogen technologies : State of the art , trends and future directions," *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 47, no. 60, pp. 25155–25201, 2022.
- [26] Q. Hassan *et al.*, "Optimizing a microgrid photovoltaic-fuel cell energy system at the highest renewable fraction," *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 47, no. 28, pp. 13710–13731, 2022.
- [27] J. Liu, Y. Zhou, H. Yang, and H. Wu, "Net-zero energy management and optimization of commercial building sectors with hybrid renewable energy systems integrated with energy storage of pumped hydro and hydrogen taxis," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 321, no. May, p. 119312, 2022.
- [28] P. Mottaghizadeh, F. Jabbari, and J. Brouwer, "Integrated solid oxide fuel cell , solar PV , and battery storage system to achieve zero net energy residential nanogrid in California," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 323, no. June, p. 119577, 2022.
- [29] M. Wei *et al.*, "Approaches to cost-effective near-net zero energy new homes with time-of-use value of energy and battery storage," *Adv. Appl. Energy*, vol. 2, no. March, p. 100018, 2021.
- [30] P. K. Cheekatamarla, "Decarbonization of residential building energy supply: Impact of cogeneration system performance on energy, environment, and economics," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 9, 2021.
- [31] C. B. Ravn Nielsen, Eva; Prag, "Learning points from demonstration of 1000 fuel cell based micro-CHP units," Copenhagen.
- [32] U.S. Department of Energy, "Prototype Building Models | Building Energy Codes Program," 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.energycodes.gov/prototype-building-models>. [Accessed: 17-Mar-2022].
- [33] S. Goel *et al.*, "Enhancements to ASHRAE standard 90.1 prototype building models," Pacific Northwest National Lab.(PNNL), Richland, WA (United States), 2014.
- [34] V. V Mendon and Z. T. Taylor, "Development of residential prototype building models and analysis system for large-scale energy efficiency studies using EnergyPlus," Pacific Northwest National Lab.(PNNL), Richland, WA (United States), 2014.
- [35] L. Brackney and A. Parker, "OpenStudio Conversion of DEER Prototypes," 2018. .
- [36] California Energy Commission, "Climate Zone tool, maps, and information supporting the California Energy Code." [Online]. Available: <https://www.energy.ca.gov/programs-and-topics/programs/building-energy-efficiency-standards/climate-zone-tool-maps-and>. [Accessed: 08-Nov-2022].
- [37] Pacific Gas & Electric, "The Pacific Energy Center's Guide to: California Climate Zones and Bioclimatic Design," 2006.
- [38] M. Sengupta, Y. Xie, A. Lopez, A. Habte, G. Maclaurin, and J. Shelby, "The National Solar Radiation Data Base (NSRDB)," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 89, no. January 2018, pp. 51–60, 2018.
- [39] C. Christensen, R. Anderson, S. Horowitz, A. Courtney, and J. Spencer, "BEopt (TM) software for building energy optimization: Features and capabilities," National Renewable Energy Lab.(NREL), Golden, CO (United States), 2006.
- [40] California Energy Commission, "2022 Single-Family Alternative Calculation Method Reference Manual, Title 24, Part 6, and Associated Administrative Regulations in Part 1," 2022.
- [41] California Energy Commission, "2019 Alternative Calculation Method Approval Manual, Title 24, Part 6, and Associated Administrative Regulations in Part 1.," 2018.
- [42] M. Bhandari and N. Fumo, "A review of ductless mini split HVAC system," *Energy Reports*, vol. 8, pp. 5930–5942, 2022.
- [43] J. Winkler, "Laboratory test report for Fujitsu 12RLS and Mitsubishi FE12NA mini-split heat pumps," National Renewable Energy Lab.(NREL), Golden, CO (United States), 2011.
- [44] Mitsubishi Electric Corporaiton, "M-Series and P-Series Catalog Winter 2021," 2021.

- [45] M. Sontag *et al.*, “Time Dependent Valuation of Energy for Developing Building Efficiency Standards,” 2020.
- [46] Southern California Edison, “Time-Of-Use Residential Rate Plans | Rates | Your Home | Home - SCE,” 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sce.com/residential/rates/Time-Of-Use-Residential-Rate-Plans>. [Accessed: 30-Nov-2022].
- [47] California Energy Commission, “SB 100 Joint Agency Report: Charting a path to a 100% Clean Energy Future,” 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.energy.ca.gov/publications/2021/2021-sb-100-joint-agency-report-achieving-100-percent-clean-electricity>. [Accessed: 06-Oct-2022].
- [48] P. Denholm, M. O’Connell, G. Brinkman, and J. Jorgenson, “Overgeneration from Solar Energy in California: A Field Guide to the Duck Chart (NREL/TP-6A20-65023),” *Tech. Rep.*, no. November, p. 46, 2015.
- [49] N. Bautista, “08/28/18- Senate Floor Analysis for Bill No. SB 100,” Sacramento, 2018.
- [50] California Public Utilities Commission, “Modernizing California’s Net Energy Metering Program to Meet Our Clean Energy Goals,” 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cpuc.ca.gov/industries-and-topics/electrical-energy/demand-side-management/net-energy-metering/nem-revisit/net-billing-tariff-fact-sheet>. [Accessed: 30-Nov-2022].
- [51] Energy and Environmental Economics Inc., “2022 Distributed Energy Resources Avoided Cost Calculator Documentation For the California Public Utilities Commission,” 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cpuc.ca.gov/-/media/cpuc-website/divisions/energy-division/documents/demand-side-management/acc-models-latest-version/2022-acc-documentation-v1a.pdf>.
- [52] California Air Resources Board, “Stationary Fuel Cell Net Energy Metering: Emission Standards | California Air Resources Board,” 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://ww2.arb.ca.gov/our-work/programs/fuel-cell-nem/emission-standards>. [Accessed: 30-Nov-2022].
- [53] Southern California Gas Company, “Natural Gas Prices | SoCalGas,” 2009. [Online]. Available: <https://www.socalgas.com/for-your-business/energy-market-services/gas-prices>. [Accessed: 30-Nov-2022].
- [54] U.S. Energy Information Administration, “Analysis & Projections Projection Data - U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA),” 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.eia.gov/analysis/projection-data.php#annualproj>. [Accessed: 30-Nov-2022].
- [55] J. Reed *et al.*, “Roadmap for the Deployment and Buildout of Renewable Hydrogen Production Plants in California,” 2020.
- [56] L. Vimmerstedt *et al.*, “2022 Annual Technology Baseline (ATB) Cost and Performance Data for Electricity Generation Technologies,” DOE Open Energy Data Initiative (OEDI); National Renewable Energy Laboratory ..., 2022.
- [57] “Assumptions to the Annual Energy Outlook 2022: Residential Demand Module,” 2022.
- [58] P. Jadun, C. McMillan, D. Stenberg, M. Muratori, L. Vimmerstedt, and T. Mai, “Electrification Futures Study: End-Use Electric Technology Cost and Performance Projections through 2050,” *Natl. Renew. Energy Lab*, p. 109, 2017.
- [59] RS Means, “Green Building Cost Data.” RSMeans, 2021.
- [60] A. Fathy, “A reliable methodology based on mine blast optimization algorithm for optimal sizing of hybrid PV-wind-FC system for remote area in Egypt,” *Renew. Energy*, vol. 95, pp. 367–380, 2016.
- [61] T. D. Huty, S. Dong, R. Lee, and S. Brown, “Long term energy storage with reversible solid oxide cells for microgrid applications,” *Energy Reports*, vol. 7, pp. 24–33, 2021.
- [62] Mathworks, “MATLAB.” Mathworks.
- [63] IBM, “CPLEX Optimization Studio.” IBM.
- [64] J. Lofberg, “YALMIP : A toolbox for modeling and optimization in MATLAB,” *IEEE Int. Symp. Comput. Aided Control Syst. Des.*, pp. 284–289, 2004.
- [65] J. Lofberg, “yalmip,” *github*, 2022. .
- [66] CEC, “California Climate Zones,” Sacramento, CA, 2006.